

Measuring Marketing Performance: An Investigation into the use of Marketing Metrics by Australian Companies

Paul Rekaris

A research report
submitted in partial fulfilment
of the requirements for the
Master of Business, 2002

School of Marketing
Faculty of Business
RMIT University
November, 2002

STATEMENT OF AUTHORSHIP

Except where reference is made in the text of the Research Project Report, this report contains no material published elsewhere or extracted in whole or in part from a thesis or report presented by me for another degree or diploma.

No other person's work has been used without due acknowledgment in the main text of the report.

This report has not been submitted for the award of any other degree or diploma in any other tertiary institution.

(Signed) (Date)

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has provided me with the opportunity to gain a valuable insight into the strategic marketing practices of some of Australia's leading companies. Needless to say, it has been a challenging, but rewarding process. I wish to thank certain individuals and organisations for their involvement in this study.

Firstly, I would like to thank the following companies for their participation: AAMI, ANZ Bank, Australia Post, Cadbury Schweppes, Carlton and United Breweries, Ford Australia, JB Were, Kmart, Origin Energy, Qantas, Village Cinemas and Telstra. Without their cooperation, this study would not have been possible and I greatly appreciate their time during both the interview stage and allowing me to ask them follow up questions.

I would like to thank my supervisor, Bill Callaghan for his help, advice and good ideas.

A special thanks to my partner, Lisa Ellis for her patience and support, and for assisting me in editing the final report.

I would also like to thank the individuals who helped me secure interviews and; my employer and my work colleagues at The Department of Innovation, Industry and Regional Development for their backing.

Finally, I would like to thank my family and friends for their wonderful encouragement and support over the last three years.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	3
KEY WORDS.....	7
ABSTRACT	7
1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND	9
1.1 Introduction	9
1.2 Background.....	11
1.2.1 The role of marketing performance measurement in a market orientated firm	11
1.2.2 Financial v marketing metrics	12
1.2.3 The development of marketing metrics.....	12
1.2.4 The use of marketing metrics in business and academic research	14
1.3 Research objectives	15
1.3.1 Major research objective	15
1.3.2 Major research questions.....	15
1.4 Importance of research and rationale for project.....	16
1.5 Research methodology	17
1.5.1 Data sources and availability	17
1.5.2 Method of data collection and analysis.....	17
2 LITERATURE REVIEW	18
2.1 Introduction	18
2.2 Background: The importance of the marketing philosophy	18
2.3 The importance of measuring marketing performance	20
2.4 The role of marketing performance measurement in a market orientated firm	23
2.5 The valuation of marketing and intangible assets.....	24
2.6 The limitation of financial measures in measuring marketing performance.....	25
2.7 The development of marketing metrics.....	27
Table 2.1. Key Metrics Categories & Marketing Measures.....	29

2.8	The absence of marketing influence at board and senior company levels....	30
2.9	The use of marketing metrics in Australian and UK firms.....	33
	Table 2.3. Top twenty marketing metrics used by UK firms.....	36
2.10	The difficulties in measuring marketing performance	36
2.11	Conclusion and implications for research questions	39
3	RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	41
3.1	Introduction	41
3.2	Research approach.....	41
3.3	Sample design	41
3.4	Justification of research methodology.....	42
3.5	Limitations of research methodology	43
3.6	Data sources and availability	45
3.7	Method of data collection	45
3.8	Qualitative data analysis.....	46
3.9	Qualitative validity and reliability.....	47
3.10	Difficulty in securing participant involvement.....	48
3.11	Conclusion.....	48
4	DATA ANALYSIS	49
4.1	Introduction	49
4.2	Data analysis for each research question	49
	Table 4.1. Key Marketing Metrics collected by respondents.....	50
	Table 4.2. Key improvements mentioned by respondents	61
4.5	Conclusion.....	65
5	CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS.....	68
5.1	Introduction	68
5.2	Conclusions of the major research objective	68
5.3	Conclusions about each research question	69

5.4	Implications for theory and practice	73
5.5	Limitations	77
5.6	Future research	78
	APPENDIX 1: DATA COLLECTED FROM RESPONDENTS.....	80
	Additional metrics collected by respondents	81
	APPENDIX 2: INTERVIEW GUIDE.....	82
	Questions.....	82
	Interview prompt card.....	84
	REFERENCES	85

KEY WORDS

Brand awareness, brand equity, competition, customer satisfaction, financial measures, innovation, intangible assets, marketing philosophy, metric, qualitative research, return on investment, shareholder value, strategy.

ABSTRACT

In order for companies to create customers and generate cash flow, it is well recognised that companies need to practise marketing. By extension, measuring marketing's effectiveness is considered central to this process. In addition, competition is driving the need for greater marketing intelligence on customers, competitors and products in the form of metrics.

The measurement of marketing performance in Australian companies is well developed and considered a serious business issue. A number of companies are beginning to develop marketing metrics scorecards for the board and senior executive management, however there is no formal system for assessing marketing metrics or the performance of the brand as part of an overall business performance management system. While key marketing metrics are reviewed by top management and some boards, they do not receive a comprehensive review of marketing performance. Key marketing metrics including customer satisfaction and loyalty are often not reviewed at board level. Brands are a firm's most valuable marketing asset, but because Australian companies do not generally practise brand valuation, marketing performance cannot be fully assessed.

While marketing metrics such as customer satisfaction and brand equity are increasingly seen as leading indicators of corporate profitability and shareholder value, marketing is seen to lack credibility because it has failed to develop links between marketing metrics and financial measures that explicitly demonstrate marketing's financial contribution to the organisation. This has influenced the assessment of marketing performance with the board and senior management giving greater emphasis to financial measures such as revenue and profitability as indicators of both corporate and marketing performance.

In order for marketing to gain greater credibility at board and CEO level, marketing needs to become more financially accountable and must develop tools and measures that demonstrate to senior management what it contributes to the organisation.

1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

The examination of marketing performance in Australian organisations is an important marketing issue requiring greater attention in both marketing and academic fields. In order for marketing to gain greater credibility, it has been widely acknowledged that there is a need for marketers to develop measures and performance systems that demonstrate the objectives they are trying to achieve.

The major objective of this research project will be to investigate how marketing performance is currently measured in Australian companies. The study will also consider the perceived value that is placed on marketing metrics in the assessment of overall business performance and the implementation of corporate strategic planning.

1.1 Introduction

In today's highly competitive business world, the role of marketing has taken on greater prominence for companies wishing to successfully compete in their chosen market. Marketing is seen as a major force driving strategic planning and business operations and has the potential to influence all levels of the organisation. According to Kotler (1999), a superior marketing strategy is the key to generating profits and creating competitive advantage. Peter Drucker (1973) claims that the one distinguishing and unique function of the business is marketing.

Every business conducts a marketing function in one form or another. Marketing and specifically customers are seen as a key driver of future cash flow opportunities (Clark 1999; Ambler, Kokkinaki, Puntoni, Riley 2001). According to a major study conducted in the United Kingdom by McKinsey and Company, 80 percent of executives surveyed believe that marketing was considered either very or critically important in helping a firm meet its financial goals (Brady, Hunter, Santiapilla 2000).

The greater focus of marketing across organisations today means that the measurement of an organisation's marketing effectiveness is therefore becoming more critical. According to Ambler and Kokkinaki (1999), measuring marketing performance may be central to business success. Assessing marketing performance is

seen as an important contemporary marketing issue with the US Marketing Science Institute listing marketing metrics as its most important research issue (Ambler et al, 2001).

There are several reasons for this emerging trend. As marketing budgets are significantly increasing, there has been a growing call for the marketing process to become more accountable (Shaw and White, 1999). Senior management is demanding greater information on how marketing expenditure is helping to achieve improvements in corporate performance. Shareholders and market analysts are also demanding more information on a firm's marketing spend and effectiveness which has traditionally received scant attention in financial reporting (Clark, 1999). There is also a growing recognition of the increasing value of intangible assets, which includes brands and market relationships. In 2000, tangible assets accounted for less than 20 percent of the value of the world's 20 largest companies Doyle (2001).

Traditionally, marketing has not played a large part in corporate strategy because of the difficulty found in efficiently measuring and communicating what marketing contributes financially to a firm's bottom line (Srivastava, Tasadduq, Shervani, Fahey, 1998). According to Drucker (1973), marketing has therefore meant more rhetoric than reality in many firms. Recent Australian studies support these claims. According to Burbury (2002), Australian boards spend only 5 percent of their time reviewing marketing related issues. Roberts and Styles (2001) claim that top management in Australian companies do not believe that marketing is a major contributor to shareholder value.

Another key driver influencing this greater focus on the measurement of marketing performance is that marketers are becoming increasingly frustrated with non-marketing measures that do not accurately measure their efforts and contribution to the organisation. The lack of credibility of marketing is seen as a major concern amongst senior marketers. According to John Stubbs, Chief Executive of the Marketing Council in the UK:

"I was taken aback by just how little reputation marketing actually has among other functions..marketing and marketers are not respected by the

people in their organisations for their contributions to business strategy, results or internal communication. We often do not know what is good or bad marketing; our measurements are not seen as credible; our qualifications are not seen to have compatible status with other professions” (Shaw and White 1999, p. 858).

For marketing to be given greater prominence at board and senior management levels, it is vital that marketers be able to justify their activities by showing either efficiency or effectiveness (Ambler et al, 2001).

1.2 Background

1.2.1 The role of marketing performance measurement in a market orientated firm

Day (1994) observes that companies who adopt market driven strategies directly relate business strategy decision making to markets, customers and competitors. The acquisition of marketing information (customer, competitor and market) or market sensing capabilities is seen as a key characteristic of a marketing orientated firm (Narver and Slater, 1990; Kohil and Jaworski, 1990; Day, 1994).

According to Day (1994), this involves a systematic, formal and anticipatory process of collecting; analysing and sharing marketing information across functions as opposed to ad hoc systems practised by inwardly driven rivals.

Marketing orientated firms consistently assess marketing information across the organisation to deliver superior customer value. Consequently, there are major performance benefits for firms that are marketing orientated (and therefore for firms who practise greater marketing intelligence and measure marketing performance), outperforming rivals who are less market driven (Narver and Slater 1990; Jaworski and Kohil, 1993). According to Ambler et al (2001), the degree to which a firm's senior management is concerned about assessing marketing performance can be explained by the extent to which they are market orientated.

1.2.2 Financial v marketing metrics

According to Ambler et al (2001), marketing measures can be generally classified as financial or non-financial measures. Assessing marketing performance in an organisation has been traditionally based on financial measures such as profit, revenue and cash flow. However, major short-term accounting measures only provide an historical snapshot of a firm's performance and provide no indication of potential future performance. Strategic decision making requires information that depicts the firm's future performance (Ambler et al, 2001). ... *'metrics act as milestones to indicate progress along each companies individual strategic direction'* (Ambler and Riley 2000, p. 1).

Eccles (1991) claims that the true business performance of a company and its growth prospects cannot be gauged by the use of financial metrics alone, but must take into account metrics such as quality, customer satisfaction, innovation and market share. *'Depending on an accounting department to reveal a company's future will leave it hopelessly mired in the past'* (Eccles 1991, p. 25). Non financial marketing measures such as brand equity, customer, channel and partner relationships are increasingly being seen as leading indicators and sources of long run shareholder value (Srivastava et al 1998; Roberts and Styles 2001; Aaker, 1996).

The increased importance of marketing measures can be seen in their inclusion in business performance assessment systems such as the balanced scorecard. This system recognises the limitations in using financial indicators as a sole measure of performance and incorporates three groups of operational measures including customer satisfaction, internal processes and innovation and learning as a source of future corporate wealth (Kaplan and Norton, 1992).

1.2.3 The development of marketing metrics

The limitation of financial measures to predict future performance has seen the development of indicators such as market share, quality, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty and brand equity (Ambler et al, 2001; Clark, 1999). According to Clark (1999), these measures have further developed into input measures (marketing

assets, marketing audit, marketing implementation and orientation) and output (efficiency, effectiveness and multi-variate) measures. However, Lehman (2002) observes that a greater understanding of the interrelationships between marketing and financial measures is required for them to be considered useful indicators of business health.

Historically, marketing performance assessment in a firm has evolved from no awareness to the use of financial metrics alone (Ambler, 1999). Companies who become more marketing focused recognise that marketing is best measured by the use of non-financial indicators. Ambler (1999) observes that while the leading indicators used by the majority of most firms number less than 100, firms that move beyond financial performance indicators and take into account marketing performance typically use around 20 indicators. In comparison, Davidson (1999) suggests 10 marketing metrics most likely to be valuable in corporate reporting.

Firms that are truly market focused balance the use of key financial indicators with the most important key marketing metrics. A study of the history of marketing performance measures recognises that there is a need to develop a set of a manageable number of indicators, while still being large enough in scope to measure marketing performance effectively (Clark, 1999).

According to Ambler, a metric should be "*precise, consistent from time to time, and place to place; sufficient (i.e. comprehensive), synchronised with the firm's objectives and necessary*" (Shaw and White 1999, p. 859). Best practice marketing firms take this process one step further by using marketing and performance indicators in order to predict future performance.

Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) have found that UK firms commonly collect nineteen individual metrics such as: brand awareness, market share, customer satisfaction, perceived quality and differentiation. These can be grouped into six metric categories which include: consumer intermediate (thoughts and feelings), consumer behaviour, trade customer, relative to competitor, innovation and financial metrics.

1.2.4 The use of marketing metrics in business and academic research

In both Australia and overseas, studies have shown that top executive management has seen very little need for the use of marketing metrics in business performance measurement systems (Kokkinaki and Ambler 1999; Roberts and Styles 2001). Styles (2000) found that the use of customer based marketing metrics by Australian boards is not common practice. There is a tendency for marketers to emphasise financial measures including sales, profit margins and return on investment over long-term marketing and customer based measures such as customer satisfaction, brand awareness and brand equity metrics. According to the study, these metrics reach only one in five boards.

A study conducted in the UK by Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) found that while there has been a greater focus on non-financial metrics such as brand equity, few companies have fully incorporated them in a formal way into their business performance measurement systems. The report found that most companies considered internal financial measures to be more important than external non-financial measures. While individual marketing metrics such as customer satisfaction and market share reach most top executive management committees, few companies have routine systems for reviewing their brands (Ambler, 2001). Only 20 percent of companies surveyed fully review their marketing performance using these measures, while only 37 percent review the value of their brand equity.

The study of marketing performance and non-financial measures has not until recently received any major attention in academic research. A study conducted by Ambler and Kokkinaki found that in over one thousand journal articles in six academic journals, only 11.5 percent of the articles related to marketing performance with non financial measures receiving little attention (Shaw and White, 1999). The study found that two of the top three measures were financial based, including sales and sales growth (47 percent of articles), market share (36 percent) and profit contribution (23 percent).

1.3 Research objectives

1.3.1 Major research objective

The major objective of this research project involves the investigation of how marketing performance is currently measured in major Australian corporations and the perceived value that is placed on marketing metrics in the assessment of overall business performance and corporate strategy.

A review of marketing performance involves a routine system of evaluating the performance of the brand over time, benchmarked against external (competitor) and internal (marketing and business plans) performance, accordingly adjusted by the gain or loss in a firm's main marketing asset during the period under review (Kokkinaki and Ambler, 1999). This includes a review of key marketing metrics, marketing programs and expenditure and a valuation of marketing assets, such as brands, key customer relationships and customer loyalty programs.

The research questions (RQ) discussed below provide a framework to investigate the major research objective.

1.3.2 Major research questions

Specifically, the research report will attempt to address the following research questions:

RQ1: What types of marketing metrics do Australian companies use to assess their marketing performance?

RQ2: Is a review of marketing performance, including a review of marketing metrics undertaken by the board of directors and senior executive management such as the CEO?

RQ3: What value does senior management place on marketing metrics in the assessment of overall business performance and are they synchronised with the firm's business objectives?

RQ4: Are companies satisfied in the way their marketing performance is measured and are there any areas that require improvement?

1.4 Importance of research and rationale for project

While it has been acknowledged that marketing has been present in a formal sense for the most part of the last century, there has been rather limited focus on the overall performance of marketing and its contribution to the organisation (Ambler, 1999). According to the US Marketing Science Institute, the performance assessment of marketing decisions and assets outside the marketing function is critical and not widely practised in a way that is relevant to senior executive management (Lehmann, 2002).

While marketing is seen as taking on greater importance, other disciplines such as accounting view marketing concepts and language as imprecise (Mazur and Shaw, 1997). There is therefore an increasing need for a greater and more precise use of customer based measures such as customer satisfaction, loyalty, perceived quality, market share, brand awareness and brand equity metrics (Amber et al, 2001; and Roberts and Styles, 2001).

In order for marketing to gain greater credibility at the strategic decision making levels of an organisation, there is a need for marketers to develop measures and performance systems that demonstrate to senior management the objectives they are trying to achieve. The US Marketing Science Institute and others argue that the marketing profession should be more focused on establishing a quantitative link between marketing and financial measures in order for marketing to become more relevant to senior management (Lehmann 2002; Srivastava et al 1998). This includes relating measures such as awareness, retention and market based assets to financial measures such as revenue, market capitalisation and shareholder growth.

The study of marketing metrics and marketing performance management systems and their value to Australian organisations is therefore a worthwhile research topic deserving a wider study in both academic and business fields.

1.5 Research methodology

1.5.1 Data sources and availability

In order to answer the research questions, primary data for this study is collected using an exploratory qualitative research approach. Specifically, this involves twelve in-depth interviews of senior marketing personnel in major Australian companies.

Sample selection for this project is based on the non-probability sampling technique of convenience sampling (Trochim, 2000). Where possible, companies are drawn from a variety of industries.

Securing interviews is an extremely difficult process due to the confidential nature of the information being sought, the seniority of the participants approached and their time constraints. This affects the total number of interviews conducted. In order to overcome this difficulty, respondents were asked to provide the names of additional respondents that were qualified on speaking on the research topic.

1.5.2 Method of data collection and analysis

Data collected from the interview process includes the type, use and the perceptions of the value of marketing measures such as brand equity and awareness measures, customer satisfaction, loyalty, retention, perceived quality, market share, relative price and new product development. An investigation of the use of marketing measurement performance systems including their role in business performance measurement systems is also assessed.

Information provided by respondents is organised into different categories and are based around the research objectives and key concepts developed throughout the research project. This allows for easier analysis and evaluation of interview results, including the extrapolation of common themes, patterns and conclusions. A discussion of possible explanations and propositions follows.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a review of the marketing performance assessment and marketing metrics literature and the theory relevant to the research questions. Specifically, the literature section covers the background of the marketing concept and its significance to the organisation, including the increasing value of marketing assets. The critical importance of measuring marketing performance in a market orientated firm is also discussed. The limitation of financial metrics in assessing marketing performance and the historical development of marketing metrics is considered. The section reviews the types of marketing metrics used by Australian and UK companies using previous research studies. The section also includes the perceived value placed on marketing and marketing performance measurement systems by senior management and the difficulties involved in measuring marketing performance.

2.2 Background: The importance of the marketing philosophy

While marketing has taken on a greater importance in modern business organisations and in business strategy, the marketing concept is not a recent phenomenon (Levitt, 1960; Drucker, 1973). First introduced as a distinct business philosophy by Peter Drucker in 1954, the invention of marketing has been attributed to a Tokyo merchant in Japan around 1650 (Drucker, 1973; Meehan and Barwise, 1996). However, it was not until around 1850 that marketing first emerged in the United States as a unique and separate function of the business firm, while marketing in Europe wasn't introduced until the 1920's. The revolution in the American economy at the turn of last century and the remarkable recovery in both the European and Japanese economies in the 1950's have been attributed to the evolution of marketing as a central business function (Drucker, 1973).

According to Drucker (1973), the purpose of a business is to create a customer and it is the customer who is responsible for the foundation of the business. Customers are the key to creating sustained competitive advantage and therefore should be at the

heart of every business decision (Kotler, 1984; Day, 1994). Marketing should therefore be the philosophy of the entire business. As the customer is central to any business and is responsible for determining what the business is and keeping it in existence, marketing is one of the major functions of any business organisation:

'Marketing is so basic that it cannot be considered a separate function within the business, on a par with others such as manufacturing or personnel.

Marketing requires separate work, and a distinct group of activities. But it is, first, a central dimension of the entire business. It is the whole business seen from the customer's point of view. Concern and responsibility for marketing must, therefore, permeate all areas of the enterprise' (Drucker 1973, p. 63).

Drucker (1973) writes that marketing sees everything from the customer's point of view and ultimately has the aim of achieving a final result such as: greater brand awareness, increased market share or customer loyalty. It is a key dimension of the firm and should be practised throughout the entire organisation. An efficient marketing strategy whose purpose is to create customer satisfaction is the key to generating profits and creating and sustaining competitive advantage (Doyle and Wong, 1998; Kotler, 1999). Doyle and Wong (1998) claim the concept of marketing as an organisational philosophy therefore has greater appeal than a functional one. *'Marketing as a management philosophy and orientation, exposed and practised throughout the corporation, is however seen increasingly as critical to the success of any organisation'* (Moorman, Trust 1999, pp. 180-197).

The importance of marketing as an organisational philosophy is a concept that is slowly beginning to be recognised in Australian companies. According to the managing director of Cadbury Confectionery in Australia and New Zealand:

"The role of marketing has moved on from probably 20 years ago, when it was a traditional silo approach. To be effective today, marketing needs to adopt a much more holistic approach to the way it goes about business and connecting with customers" (Burbury 2002, p. 28).

2.3 The importance of measuring marketing performance

It has been suggested previously that in order for companies to create customers and generate cash flow, companies need to practise marketing. By extension, measuring marketing performance is therefore crucial to this process. Additionally, a company is more likely to achieve what it measures (Drucker 1973; Eccles; 1991; Ambler 1999; 2000). ‘*What gets measured gets attention, particularly when rewards are tied to measures*’ (Eccles 1991, p. 25).

Drucker (1973) writes that the measurement of performance is one of key tasks of management: ‘*The fourth basic element in the work of a manager is measurement. The manager establishes yardsticks-and few factors are as important to the performance of the organisation and of every man in it*’ (Drucker 1973, p. 400).

Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) claim that measuring marketing performance may also be central to the tenet of business success. Non-financial measures including marketing measures may be leading indicators of corporate performance and greater shareholder value (Srivastava et al, 1998; Davidson, 1999). Davidson (1999) claims that analysts place nearly as much value on certain marketing metrics as they do on financial metrics, while Lehmann (2002) observes that product quality, customer satisfaction and market share are positively related to financial indicators such as revenue, return on investments and lower costs.

In the UK, it has been found that companies that consistently reported more marketing information outperformed the FTSE index (Ambler, 2002). Companies that report marketing metrics have a greater chance of meeting their marketing goals. Furthermore, the disclosure of metrics gives shareholders and analysts the perception that the company recognises the importance of the market and has a strong understanding of it.

Measuring marketing performance through the creation of marketing metrics enables firms to see how marketing contributes to a firm’s profitability, therefore making marketing more accountable and ultimately giving it greater credibility throughout the organisation. Ambler (2000) suggests that metrics add more meaning to marketing

terms such as brand loyalty. Establishing both short and long term metrics, achieving agreement on the set of metrics to be used, setting performance goals against these metrics and measuring success against them is an important part of the process (McCullough, 2000).

The measurement of marketing performance through the use of marketing metrics can also help discourage short termism (Ambler, 2000). The nature of financial markets means that companies focus on improving short term revenue, while gains in long term profitability that can be achieved through activities such as brand building is often not taken into account (McCullough, 2000). A focus on the right marketing performance measures can give a company a long-term orientation regarding profitability and market pressures. Additionally, marketing metrics such as brand equity can act as a leading indicator when a firm's short-term profits may be misleadingly high.

Marketers are under greater pressure today to justify their growing budgets and to show how marketing expenditure and other customer related activities help drive improvements in company performance (Shaw and White, 1999). Wallace (2002) claims that marketing budgets for Australian companies have grown 9 percent since 1999 and were expected to grow a total of 18.6 percent by the end of the 2003 financial year. Some commentators have even questioned the value of costly marketing programs to corporate success (Brady and Davis 1993; Shaw and White 1999). According to Brady and Davis (1993): '*large marketing departments, which far from being an asset, are often a millstone around an organisation's neck*' (Brady and Davis 1993, p. 17).

Shaw and White (1999) observe there are four main reasons why it is becoming increasingly important for marketing to become more accountable. Firstly, because of the increasing cost of marketing programs and the increasing link between marketing intangible assets such as brands and company performance, both financial analysts and investors are seeking greater information on marketing performance. According to one leading Australian marketing consultant:

“Investing in intangible assets to differentiate yourself certainly is an increasing trend. CEOs are also being made more accountable than ever for a company's performance both in market capitalisation and brand value. And that accountability is coming from analysts, media institutions and even mum and dad shareholders” (Burbury 2002, p. 30).

A survey conducted in the UK of senior company executives claims that greater marketing information such as brand equity should be disclosed to shareholders in annual reports (Ambler, 2002). Put simply, shareholders are entitled to the right to know what companies are doing about the creation of future shareholder value.

Secondly, developments outside traditional areas of marketing such as customer service improvement programs, call centres, distribution channels and information technology have resulted in the demand for greater marketing information. Thirdly, human resources require information on marketing performance and customer related goals in order to design employee incentive schemes, review employment performance and implement cultural change programs. By directly linking marketing activities with other areas of the company, marketing becomes aligned with a firm's overall corporate objectives and strategy, giving marketing a much greater influence throughout the company. Finally, there has been an increasing use of non-financial performance measures in overall business performance measurement systems such as the balanced scorecard.

While it is widely recognised that marketers must become more accountable, one senior marketer in the UK claims that this issue is not a major priority for most marketing directors (Ambler, 2000). For example, while the measurement of marketing communications programs is important, there are only a few firms that pay their agencies by results. In the future it is expected that marketing and agency firms will be required to become more accountable and that this type of arrangement will become more widely practised.

2.4 The role of marketing performance measurement in a market orientated firm

Day (1994) writes that companies who adopt market driven strategies directly relate business strategy decision making to markets, customers and competitors. The acquisition of marketing information and intelligence (customer, competitor and market) or market sensing capabilities is seen as a key characteristic of a marketing orientated firm (Narver and Slater, 1990; Kohil and Jaworski, 1990; Day, 1994; Doyle and Wong, 1998). *'assessment of customer needs is the cornerstone of a market orientation'* (Kohil and Jaworski 1990, p. 4).

Day (1994) observes that this is seen as specifically involving a systematic, formal and anticipatory process of collecting; analysing and sharing marketing information across functions, as opposed to ad hoc systems practised by inwardly driven rivals. Marketing orientated firms consistently assess marketing information across the organisation to deliver superior customer value. For example, Narver and Slater (1990) have found that the measurement of customer satisfaction was highly correlated with customer and market orientation: *'Specifically, customer orientation is the sufficient understanding of one's target buyers to be able to create superior value for them continuously'* (Narver and Slater 1990, p. 21).

Consequently, there are major performance benefits for firms that are marketing orientated (and therefore for firms who practise greater marketing intelligence and measure marketing performance), outperforming rivals who are less market driven (Narver and Slater 1990; Jaworski and Kohil, 1993; Slater and Narver 1994; Meehan and Barwise, 1996; Kokkinaki and Ambler, 1999). Therefore the degree to which a firm's senior management is concerned about assessing marketing performance can be explained by the extent to which they are market orientated (Ambler, Kokkinaki, Puntoni and Riley, 2001).

Meehan and Barwise (1996) contend that a company cannot be market orientated without good market sensing and that a firm's ability to create customer value and competitive advantage depends significantly on its market sensing capabilities. This relates to management's ability to understand its current and potential customers

needs and wants and its competitor offerings. They observed firms that practise market sensing activities enjoy superior business performance. When a company's management is armed with a greater understanding of the market, its ability to offer greater competitor offerings is enhanced, therefore gaining greater market share, sales growth and increased profitability.

2.5 The valuation of marketing and intangible assets

It is increasingly becoming recognised that the creation of corporate wealth and greater shareholder value depends greatly on the management of intangible assets including brands, market relationships, human capital, intellectual property, knowledge and research and development (Ambler 2002; Doyle 2001; Aaker, 1996; Kaplan and Norton, 1996). There is also evidence that the valuation of marketing assets is beginning to appear outside marketing in management, economics and accounting journals (Lehmann, 2002). Specifically, examples of marketing assets include brand and market based relationships such as customer, channel and partner relationships (Srivastava et al 1998).

It has been estimated that 70 percent of the market value of the Fortune 500 companies comprises intangible assets (Srivastava et al, 1998). For example, according to Simms (2001), the value of Coca-Cola's tangible assets such as its plants and machinery accounts for only 7 percent of its total assets. The remaining value is made up of intangible assets, mostly its marketing assets including its brand. Market based assets can lead to lower costs, price premiums, competitive barriers and switching costs, provide a competitive edge and provide managers with greater options (Srivastava et al, 1998).

While marketing assets may have no formal place on a firm's balance sheet, their importance is now widely recognised (Kokkinaki and Ambler, 1999). *'Back in the 1980s, no firms were formally measuring brand equity. By 2010, no professionally managed business will fail to do so'* (Ambler 2000, p. 5).

According to Ambler (2002), measures such as brand equity represent a large share of unrealised future cash flow, which serves to act as a balance between the assessment

of short-term performance and longer-term expectations: *'The marketing asset is essential for evaluating marketing performance for a very simple reason: marketing activities in one financial period show up on the bottom line in other periods'*

(Ambler and Kokkinaki 1999, p. 30).

Brand equity is often cited as the reason why a company's market value is greater than its true accounting value. For many cases, brand equity is one of a company's most valuable assets, therefore a company's financial performance cannot be properly evaluated without analysing and measuring it (Ambler, 2002).

While brand equity is considered an intangible asset and is difficult to measure, research suggests that for some of the very well known brands, it can be worth fifty to seventy percent of a company's total assets (Superbrands Council, 1997). For example, Coca-Cola estimates that its brand is worth more than US \$39 billion (Court, Freeling, Leiter and Parsons, 1997). While according to Thakor (1996), Philip Morris bought Kraft for US \$13 billion, more than six times its book value.

2.6 The limitation of financial measures in measuring marketing performance

Ambler et al (2001) claim that marketing measures can be generally classified as financial or non-financial measures. Assessing marketing performance in an organisation has been traditionally based on financial measures such as profit, revenue and cash flow. While companies routinely track a range of non-financial measures such as market share and quality, they are not given equal prominence as financial measures in determining strategy, promotions, bonuses, and other rewards (Eccles, 1991).

If marketing's main objective is to capture customer preference by satisfying customer needs, internal financial measures are insufficient in order to adequately assess marketing performance (Kokkinaki and Ambler, 1999). A true indication of marketing performance can only be determined by using external or market measures. Major short-term accounting measures only provide an historical snapshot of a firm's

performance and provide no indication of potential future performance (Kaplan and Norton, 1996).

The true business performance of a company and its growth prospects cannot be gauged by the use of financial metrics alone, but must take into account metrics such as brand equity, customer satisfaction, loyalty, quality, innovation and market share (Eccles 1991; Clark 1999). *'Depending on an accounting department to reveal a company's future will leave it hopelessly mired in the past'* (Eccles 1991, p. 25). Eccles (1991) claims the 1980s saw a marked deterioration in business performance of major corporations because of the lack of close observation in quality, customer satisfaction and loss of market share to major global competitors.

Strategic decision making requires information that depicts the firm's future performance (Ambler et al, 2001). *... 'metrics act as milestones to indicate progress along each company's individual strategic direction'* (Ambler and Riley 2000, p. 1).

In the future, senior management will be required to synchronise indicators of business performance more closely with corporate strategy. Drucker writes: *'To manage in the future, executives will need an information system integrated with strategy, rather than individual tools that so far have been used largely to record the past'* (Drucker 1995, p. 54).

An extensive study by Ernst & Young (2002) found that non-financial measures including measures such as brands, market share, customer satisfaction and innovation are crucial to the valuation of US companies. The study found that 35 percent of investment analysts' decisions were attributed to non-financial measures and the more this type of information was taken into account, the more accurate their earnings forecasts were. The study claims that reliance by companies on financial measures alone could undermine their long-term survival.

The increased importance of marketing measures can be seen in their inclusion in business performance assessment systems such as the balanced scorecard which combines both financial and non financial measures including customer metrics in order to gain an overall view of company performance. This system recognises the

limitations in using financial indicators to measure performance and incorporates three groups of operational measures including customer satisfaction, internal processes, innovation and learning as sources of future corporate wealth (Kaplan and Norton, 1992; 1996).

The measurement and improvement of marketing performance is an integral part of the balanced scorecard. Specifically, the core measures of customer satisfaction include market share, customer retention, customer acquisition, and customer profitability. Measures and objectives developed around these value propositions are targeted towards specific customers and segments. The company's customer perspective of the scorecard can then be translated into a company's strategy which can be communicated throughout the organisation.

2.7 The development of marketing metrics

Dissatisfaction with the use of financial indicators to measure business performance is not a new issue (Eccles, 1991). In 1951, General Electric commissioned a high level project in order to identify key non financial business performance measures. Evidence suggests that companies are slowly beginning to realise the importance of non-financial measures. Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) observe that the US Institute of Management Accounting claims the use of non-financial indicators between 1992 and 1996 grew from half to two-thirds of companies, while 90 percent expect that figure to increase. A further sixty four percent of financial controllers were actively experimenting with new methods of collecting and reporting non-financial data (Ernst & Young, 2002).

Ambler and Kokkinaki (1997) have found that the terminology used to describe marketing performance has not been clear. The term '*metric*' has been proposed to define a '*top-level measure of marketing performance*', and the term '*diagnostic*' to describe variances in metrics (Shaw and White, 1999). A metric should be "*precise, consistent from time to time, and place to place; sufficient (i.e. comprehensive), synchronised with the firm's objectives and necessary*" (Shaw and White 1999, p. 859). According to Ambler (2000), in order for a metric to be considered reliable it should be relevant, that is, it should be reviewed by top management and should

matter to the whole business. Metrics may be financial (for example, profit and loss statement), market based or from non-financial internal sources (for example, innovation; and employee).

The limitation of financial measures to predict future performance has seen the development of a range of indicators that measure brand strength and market performance such as market share, quality, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, retention and brand equity (Ambler et al, 2001; Clark, 1999; Eccles, 1991). These measures have further developed into input measures (marketing assets, marketing audit, marketing implementation and orientation) and output (efficiency, effectiveness and multivariate) measures. However, Lehmann (2002) and Clark (1999) observe that a greater understanding of the interrelationships between marketing metrics and financial measures such as shareholder growth is needed for them to be considered useful indicators of business health.

According to Ambler (1999), marketing performance assessment in a firm has historically evolved from no awareness to the use of financial metrics alone. Companies who become more marketing focused recognise that marketing is best measured by the use of non-financial indicators. While the leading indicators used by the majority of most firms number less than 100, firms who move beyond financial performance indicators and take into account marketing performance typically use around 20 indicators (Ambler, 1999). Firms that are truly market focused balance the use of key financial indicators with the most important key marketing metrics. Clark (1999) observes that the number of indicators needs to be manageable, while still being large enough in scope to measure marketing performance effectively. Best practice marketing firms take this process one step further by using marketing and performance indicators in order to predict future performance. As mentioned previously, marketing intangible assets or brand equity is a major source of shareholder wealth and brand equity metric measures such as brand awareness and brand loyalty measures have taken on greater importance. (Aaker, 1996; Davidson, 1999).

Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) propose that in order for an organisation to successfully measure their marketing performance three criteria are required:

comparisons with market or non financial internal (e.g. business and marketing plans) and external benchmarks (e.g. competition, market), accordingly adjusted by changes in the gain or loss in the firm's main marketing asset, which is usually brand equity during the period under review.

Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) have found that on average, UK firms use six metric categories when measuring marketing performance. They have identified nineteen metrics that are commonly reviewed by senior management which are perceived to be of importance when assessing marketing performance. These measures have been classified into the following categories: financial, competitive market, consumer behaviour, consumer intermediate (thoughts and feelings), direct trade customer and innovation. These six metric categories are described in detail in table 2.1.

Table 2.1. Key Metrics Categories & Marketing Measures

Metrics category	Metrics
Consumer Intermediate	Awareness Perceived quality Consumer satisfaction Relevance to consumer Perceived differentiation Brand/ product knowledge
Consumer Behaviour	Number of new consumers Loyalty/retention Conversions
Trade Customer	Customer satisfaction Number of complaints
Relative to competitor	Relative consumer satisfaction Perceived quality
Innovation	Number of new products Revenue of new products Margin of new products
Financial	Sales Gross margins Profitability

Source: Ambler & Riley, London Business School (2000)

In comparison, Davidson (1999) has found ten marketing metrics that are most likely to be valuable in corporate reporting. They include: market trend, market share, major brand trends, customer retention, new product performance, unit volume trend, research and development trend, capital expenditure, total marketing investment and distribution trend. Furthermore, metrics were chosen using the following criteria:

importance to analysts, practical ability to report, importance to management and economic importance to most companies.

2.8 The absence of marketing influence at board and senior company levels

While it is widely recognised that marketing influences a firm's future profits, firms have traditionally paid little attention to the assessment of marketing assets and marketing performance (Ambler, 1999). For example, only ten companies in the UK FSTE 350 companies report the valuation of brands on their balance sheets (Smith, 2001). Additionally, the linking of marketing strategies to shareholder value has received limited attention (Srivastava et al 1998). Davidson (1999) reports that analysts in the UK are dissatisfied with the level of disclosure of marketing data.

According to leading marketing strategists, Australian boards spend only 5 percent of their time reviewing issues related to brands, marketing, competition, and new opportunities (Burbury, 2002). Research has shown that senior management in Australian companies believe that marketing is not a key driver of shareholder value (Burbury 2002; Roberts and Styles, 2000). Styles (2000) found that only 22 percent of Australian CEOs and 11 percent of Board of Directors believe that marketing is a major contributor to shareholder value. According to McCullough (2000), boards do not recognise marketing's contribution to business profitability and instead perceive marketing as an expense where there is no known return.

Simms (2001) observes that a large factor behind the perception of marketing and its lack of influence at senior level is that few chief executives have marketing backgrounds. In the UK, only 13 FSTE chief executives are considered having marketing backgrounds. The remainder come from backgrounds including law, banking, engineering and IT.

A UK study by McKinsey and Company claims that while marketing was becoming more important in achieving financial objectives, marketing was not a well-developed discipline in two thirds of companies (Brady et al, 2000). The same survey found that while marketing was heavily linked to corporate and business unit strategic decision

making, there was a greater need for marketing to collaborate with other areas of the organisation and also a greater need for clear and quantified performance metrics. While organisations have much marketing information at their disposal, marketing efforts with the rest of the organisation are largely uncoordinated (Ambler, 1999).

In Australia, many marketers complain that senior management of leading companies do not have a good understanding of the role of marketing and the interrelationships that exist between marketing, sales and other intangible assets such as brand equity (Burbury, 2002). Additionally, it has been found that there is no distinction between a company's overall strategic efforts to succeed in the market and the marketing department's activities.

Many CEOs perceive marketing to mean advertising, promotions and packaging and therefore see marketing as filling a brand and marketing communications role rather than a key strategic one in what the company needs to do to succeed in the market place: *'It also means that the CEO isn't fully across how marketing return on investment should be reported and, therefore, what key marketing metrics should be reported at board level'* (Burbury 2002, p. 30).

There is an increasing call for CEOs to become advocates of the concept of the market driven company and promote the understanding of how marketing can contribute to shareholder value and corporate reputation (Burbury, 2002).

Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) have found that the perception of marketing affects the way in which it is viewed and measured in organisations. In the UK, it has been estimated that on average, boards spend ninety percent of their time on measuring cash flow and only 10 percent analysing its sources and creating new business opportunities (Ambler, 2000). For example, only 40 percent of companies review brand equity at board level, while only 36 percent view data on customer satisfaction. This means that boards generally receive little, if any perspective of a firm's overall marketing performance.

The lack of assessment in marketing performance also affects the way in which marketing is seen. Doyle (2001) claims that marketing is seen by top management as

unsophisticated and not as highly developed as other disciplines such as economics or finance. In the UK, other non marketing departments such as finance perceive that marketing lacks in the areas of strategic thinking, creative problem solving and generally doing things well (Ambler and Kokkinaki, 1999). According to McKinsey and Company, the finance profession does not think that marketing is important in helping companies achieve their financial objectives (Brady et al, 2000). Because the marketing discipline has found it difficult in the past to communicate to other areas the financial value created by marketing activities, it has played a limited role in the formation of strategy (Srivastava et al, 1998). However, as the role of marketing continues to evolve and its influence increases throughout the organisation, there will be a greater need for marketing to integrate with other disciplines such as finance (Srivastava et al, 1998).

Adding to differences between finance and marketing are different priorities, agendas and times scales (Simms, 2001). For example, the finance director's time frame is short term and includes objectives such as cost reduction and maximising return on investment. Marketing on the other hand is concerned with building long-term brand value and creating superior products for its customers.

Research conducted among the FSTE 500 companies found that finance directors view marketing with great scepticism and see its directors as unaccountable, untouchable, slippery and expensive (Simms, 2001). Marketing is also primarily seen as dealing with emotional values and subjective ideas:

'marketers are confronted by general low regard of their discipline, as a consequence of a number of longstanding weaknesses associated with it.... Yet poor image and lack of secure skill and knowledge base continue to dog marketing and marketers in many organisations in the UK. The problem of poor image seems to arise where marketing has allowed itself to become merely a sales support function, or where companies have tried and failed to implement certain aspects of marketing' (Denison and McDonald 1995, pp. 54-76).

Denison and McDonald (1995) claim that if marketing does not respond to the challenges it is presented with, it risks becoming marginalised as a discipline. In order for marketing to gain greater credibility, marketing performance assessment has been earmarked as a key marketing challenge.

2.9 The use of marketing metrics in Australian and UK firms

In both Australia and the UK, studies have shown that top executive management has seen very little need for the use of marketing metrics in business performance measurement systems (Kokkinaki and Ambler 1999; Roberts and Styles 2000). While individual marketing metrics such as customer satisfaction and market share reach most top executive management committees, few companies have routine systems for reviewing their brands (Ambler, 2001).

Styles (2000) has found that the use of customer based marketing metrics by Australian boards is not common practice. According to the study, there is a tendency for marketers in Australia to emphasise financial measures including sales, profit margins and return on investment over long-term marketing and customer based measures such as customer satisfaction, brand awareness and brand equity. According to the study, these metrics reach only one in five boards. Roberts and Styles (2000) suggest that marketers need to place less emphasis on traditional accounting measures when evaluating marketing performance.

Table 2.2. Marketing Measures used by Australian firms

Measure	% Top importance rating	% Reach board of directors
Financial		
Margins	81	46
Sales	78	52
ROI	73	58
Profit (accounting)	71	59
Marketing		
Perceived quality	62	14
Customer satisfaction	62	22
Market share	53	33
Marketing spend	51	28
Brand awareness	49	20
Brand equity/health	48	21
Brand image	46	9
Differentiation	46	8
Relative image	38	9
Relative quality	35	6
Loyalty/retention	35	6
Distribution/availability	34	3
Relative satisfaction	33	5
Relative price	32	8
Brand value	28	35

Source: Styles, University of NSW (2000)

As shown in table 2.2, the top four marketing measures used by Australian corporations surveyed are all financial. Further, only 22 percent of the board of directors see information regarding customer satisfaction, 20 percent on brand awareness and 21 percent on brand equity/health. The study also found that only 12 percent of respondents perceived measuring marketing effectiveness to be a current key marketing challenge, while only 7 percent saw it as a key challenge in the future.

A major study by Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) conducted in the UK also found that financial metrics were the leading measures used when assessing marketing performance. The study claims that while there has been a greater focus on non-financial metrics such as brand equity, few companies have fully incorporated them in a formal way into their business performance measurement systems. The study found that marketers are not satisfied with the way in which marketing effectiveness is being measured. This is because most companies consider internal financial measures to be

more important than external non-financial measures such as customer satisfaction. Only 20 percent of companies surveyed review their marketing performance using the previously mentioned measurement criteria (comparisons with internal market and external benchmarks, adjusted by changes in firm's brand equity), while only 37 percent review the value of their brand equity. Additionally, Ambler (2000) suggests that marketing plans are predominantly financial documents with financial measures such as sales, costs and profits given greater importance than marketing metrics.

The survey found that 44 percent of respondents use financial measures to assess their marketing performance, followed by consumer intermediate (26 percent), competitor market (14 percent), consumer behaviour (14 percent), direct trade (2 percent) and innovation (0.8 percent). Financial metrics including profits (91 percent), sales (91 percent) and gross margins (81 percent) were the leading metrics gathered. Brand awareness (78 percent), market share (78 percent) and number of new products (73%) were the leading market metrics collected.

The same study also found that when measuring marketing effectiveness, UK company boards prefer key financial data such as profits and sales (Ambler et al, 2001). The study found that the three top measures assessed by boards were all financial and included profits (80 percent of all boards), sales (71 percent), and gross margin (58 percent). Only 36 percent of boards review data on client satisfaction, 33 percent on market share and 28 percent looked at brand awareness. Table 2.3 lists the leading brand equity measures found in the survey.

Table 2.3. Top twenty marketing metrics used by UK firms

Metric	Firms using measure (%)	Reach board of directors (%)	Top rating for assessing marketing performance (%)
Profit	91	73	80
Sales (volume or value)	91	65	71
Gross margin	81	58	20
Awareness	78	28	28
Market share (volume or value)	78	33	36
Number of new products	73	24	25
Relative price (share of market/volume)	70	34	37
Number of complaints	69	30	45
Customer satisfaction	68	36	46
Distribution/availability	66	11	18
Total number of customers	65	37	40
Perceived quality	64	32	35
Loyalty/retention	64	51	67
Marketing expenditure	64	71	63
Relative perceived quality	62	53	62
Number of new customers	57	48	57
Brand/product knowledge	55	42	44
Image/personality/identity	54	43	56
Shareholder value	52	84	79
Perceived differentiation	50	46	49

Source: Ambler (2000)

2.10 The difficulties in measuring marketing performance

While the assessment of marketing performance has been an appealing concept for both marketers and marketing academics, it has not been widely practised (Ambler, 1999). It has been recognised that marketing performance is a difficult concept to measure: *'perhaps no other concept in marketing's short history has proven as stubbornly resistant to conceptualisation, definition, or application as that of marketing performance'* (Bonoma and Clark 1988, p. 1).

While much work has taken place in the research of key marketing inputs, the measurement of marketing performance or outputs has remained a difficult field to both define and conceptualise and has therefore received limited application in business and academic fields (Bonoma and Clark, 1988; Amber and Kokkinaki, 1997;

Shaw and White, 1999; Burbury, 2002). According to Shaw and White (1999), marketing outputs can include outcomes such as market leadership, distribution leadership, price premium and brand valuation.

There are a number of reasons why marketing performance has traditionally received limited attention (Bonoma and Clark, 1988; Shaw and White, 1999; Kokkinaki and Ambler, 1999). In the past, marketers have placed greater emphasis on the achievement of results rather than their measurement (Bonoma and Clark 1988; Ambler and Kokkinaki, 1999). Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) claim that this has led to an overemphasis on financial indicators. Marketers aims in the past have therefore not been as defined when compared to pure financial objectives. Shaw and Mazur contend that marketing executives' major gripe with marketing is due to the perception that they do not take the measurement of performance seriously (Kokkinaki and Ambler, 1999). It has been perceived that marketers have not taken responsibility for measurement and have viewed it as a support role, outsourcing it to other departments such as finance (Ambler and Kokkinaki, 1999). Consequently, this has affected the credibility of the role of marketing in many organisations. For example, according to David Norton, marketing does not play any role in the development of company's balanced scorecards (Shaw and White, 1999). Scorecard data is more than likely processed by strategic planners or finance.

Another major factor why marketing performance has received scant attention is because the marketing discipline cuts across both many internal and external functions of the organisation such as production and distribution channels (Bonoma and Clark, 1988). Marketing's influence is therefore both complicated and far-reaching, influencing exogenous players that are uncontrolled to the organisation such as customers and suppliers. This makes measurement much more complicated.

Bonoma and Clark (1988) observe that marketing in many cases represents the face of the corporation, the needs of its customers and the firm's goals and objectives. Marketing is expected to make links between the firm's objectives and its outputs. However many of these results are lagged and are subject to a number of influences, that establishing cause and effect linkages is difficult.

Determining the contribution of marketing activities to short and long term effects is therefore complicated. For example, determining the effectiveness of marketing and promotional expenditure is virtually impossible (Brady and Davis, 1993). Another challenge is the difficulty in relating soft data such as customer attitudes to performance (Ambler and Riley, 2000).

Additionally, the development of marketing metrics is complicated by other factors on how performance should be assessed such as whether one should be concerned with efficiency (return on investment) or effectiveness (achieving the right strategic goals) (Bonoma and Clark 1988; Ambler 1999; Ambler and Kokkinaki 1999). According to Bonoma and Clark (1988), marketing literature has paid little attention to the effectiveness of marketing and instead has focused on its efficiency. Further complicating performance measurement is that because marketing success requires companies to outperform their rivals; the assessment of marketing performance has to be evaluated against competitor performance.

Marketing's focus on the measurement of inputs is reflected in the limited amount of academic research in the measurement of marketing performance (Bonoma and Clark, 1988; Ambler and Kokkinaki, 1997; 1999). It has also been found that the terminology used to describe marketing performance is not precise or consistent. According to Ambler (1999), translating marketing survey results into useable marketing metrics requires a well thought out approach because much of the raw survey data cannot be easily turned into ratios such as market share, relative price, brand loyalty etc. The lack of academic research in this area has most likely influenced companies' marketing measurement performance activities.

2.11 Conclusion and implications for research questions

This section has reviewed the relevant marketing performance literature and theory relevant to the research objectives, including the importance of measuring marketing performance and a historical development of marketing assessment.

Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) found that when assessing marketing performance, on average top level management reviews nineteen metrics in six metric categories.

These include: financial, competitive market, consumer behaviour, consumer intermediate, direct trade customer and innovation. 78 percent of firms collect information on brand awareness and market share, while 68 percent use a customer satisfaction measure.

Studies in both Australia and the UK show that while there is a large focus in measuring marketing performance through the use of marketing metrics, few have fully incorporated them in an overall business performance measurement system. Consequently, the marketing profession is dissatisfied with their marketing performance measurement systems.

While it was acknowledged that the assessment of marketing performance is an emerging and critical issue to the discipline of marketing and the assessment of corporate performance, it has been a difficult concept to measure and has traditionally received limited attention at senior executive and board level. Top management and boards do not recognise the value of marketing metrics in the assessment of overall business performance and therefore do not receive a comprehensive view of marketing performance. While key marketing metrics reach executive management committees, it has been found that top management places a greater emphasis on financial measures such as sales and profit margins when assessing marketing performance. Financial measures also dominate marketing metrics in marketing plans. However, the true business performance and the future growth potential of a company cannot be assessed through the use of financial indicators, but must take into account marketing metrics such as brand equity, loyalty, customer satisfaction and market share.

Top management and boards see marketing as unsophisticated and a less highly developed discipline such as finance. This is because marketers have found it difficult to establish how their discipline's activities contribute to the company's bottom line. There is also no clear link between marketing metrics and financial measures such as revenue and shareholder growth. Consequently, marketing's role in strategy has been limited.

The following chapter provides a description and justification of the research methodology used in the research project.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter contains a description of the methodology research approach that was adopted throughout the project. Specifically, the chapter presents a discussion of the sample selection and the data collection method, an evaluation of the research methodology, including the justification and limitations of the approach taken and a discussion of the methodology's validity and reliability.

3.2 Research approach

In order to answer the research questions, primary data was collected using an exploratory qualitative research approach. Specifically, this involved eleven face to face in-depth interviews and one telephone interview of senior marketing personnel in major Australian companies.

Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) observe that this is a sound approach as larger organisations are expected to represent best practice in terms of marketing measurement methods.

Qualitative research can be defined as information that is collected in a narrative form by conducting interviews and through making observations (Sekaran, 2000).

While qualitative research has traditionally been used in the academic fields of the social sciences such as anthropology, history and political science, it has recently taken on greater prominence in applied fields such as business studies and public administration (Miles and Huberman, 1994).

3.3 Sample design

The sample, a group of respondents who are selected to be involved in the study, is a subset of the larger population and is used to make conclusions regarding the entire population (Trochim, 2000; Zikmund, 2000).

Sample selection for this project was primarily based on the non-probability sampling technique of convenience sampling which involves selecting respondents based on personal judgement (Trochim, 2000; Zikmund, 2000).

Companies involved in the study were approached based on matters of convenience and included a consideration of a wide range of factors including cost, location of head office and availability and access to senior marketing personnel. Where possible, companies were chosen from a variety of industries including telecommunications, financial services, retail and fast moving consumer goods.

Respondents were asked to provide the names of additional respondents that were qualified on speaking on the research topic. According to Burns and Bush (2000), this is referred to as a snowball sample.

3.4 Justification of research methodology

One of the major justifications for conducting qualitative research is that it allows the researcher to become more experienced in their chosen topic (Trochim, 2000).

Qualitative research provides the researcher with direct experience of the phenomenon that they are studying, which may be missing when using a quantitative research approach. According to Trochim (2000), this direct experience has been lacking in applied social research. While the nature of qualitative research is considered by many to be exploratory and inductive, it can be used to prove a very specific deductive hypothesis and can be used to confirm most types of research questions (Trochim, 2000).

Qualitative research and more specifically in-depth interviewing allows the researcher to meet face to face with the respondents. Trochim (2000) suggests that this approach helps to generate information and insights and allows the researcher to discuss the research problem in richer detail.

Qualitative data provides the researcher with a source of meaningful, rich and vivid descriptions and explanations of observations and processes that can be more convincing to the reader (Miles and Huberman, 1994). Qualitative research allows

the researcher to replicate and represent logical flows and links and present more meaningful analysis of the research under investigation. Good qualitative data can also help a researcher develop a sound conceptual framework of their research findings. Miles and Huberman (1994) observe that research results presented through words and in a meaningful way can be more convincing to a reader including researchers, business and policy makers than results presented in a quantitative format.

Hastings and Perry (2000) suggest that qualitative research allows analytical generalisations or theory building to take place that lay the foundations for statistical testing or quantitative research to occur.

According to Zikmund (2000), in depth interviews offer the researcher many advantages. Face to face interaction with respondents allows the researcher to obtain greater and more exact information. Interviews allow flexibility as the researcher can repeat and rephrase questions in order to clarify ambiguities so the questions are more easily understood, while there is also an opportunity to provide feedback to the respondent and gain additional information through probing and asking follow up questions (Zikmund, 2000; Sekaran, 2000). The researcher is also able to pick up non-verbal cues from the respondent, enabling a better understanding of the respondent's answer.

As most research projects have stringent time and budget constraints, convenience sampling enables the researcher to collect information quickly and economically and is not labour intensive (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Zikmund, 2000).

3.5 Limitations of research methodology

Zikmund (2000) claims that qualitative research techniques involve several limitations. A major criticism of qualitative research is that it is considered subjective and the majority of the research process is left to the personal judgement and intuition of the researcher, while samples are not considered representative of the entire population. Qualitative research differs from quantitative research in that it does not involve rigorous mathematical analysis and exact measurement. Additionally, results are difficult to generalise. The drawbacks of qualitative research may affect the

findings and the final conclusions of the research project. Geographical limitations also restrict which respondent companies are involved, while it can also add cost to the research project.

According to Miles and Huberman (1994), the use of convenience sampling may mean that the research project lacks objectivity, credibility and misses information, while generalising results beyond the specific convenience sample may lead to incorrect conclusions and therefore may not be useful for decision making purposes.

Additionally, because qualitative research involves the study of small samples, the convenience sampling method may not be representative of the population that is being studying (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Trochim, 2000). Trochim (2000) suggests that when designing the sample, there is the potential for introducing systematic error or bias in a project and ultimately this may affect the research report's results.

Due to budgetary, logistical and time constraints, a small sample of twelve large companies was used for this research project. As companies interviewed were both large and Melbourne based (with the exception of one respondent), this may have caused further bias in the project. However, the project's qualitative approach allowed probing questions to be asked which revealed insights, values and a deeper understanding about the use of marketing measurement systems that may not have been revealed in the use of quantitative data alone.

According to Trochim (2000), while qualitative research provides more detailed information, the data is usually collected in a raw format and is rarely pre-categorised. This makes it difficult to determine what the universal themes are and how they relate to each other. This is a challenging issue in qualitative research as analysing data is both time consuming and labour intensive. This can add to the cost and the time taken to complete the research project.

Another drawback in conducting in-depth interviews is that due to the lack of anonymity, respondents may be reluctant to reveal confidential information to the researcher. This may affect the information and data collected from respondents.

Further, respondents interviewed must also be knowledgeable on the topic area or this may affect the research results (Hasting and Perry 2000). This limitation was somewhat overcome by using a snowball sampling technique by asking respondents to identify individuals with the necessary expertise in order to conduct further interviews.

The research report did not involve quantitative analysis because cost and time constraints did not allow the collection of an adequate sample in order to conduct a meaningful analysis. In a research project, the quality of data collected must be balanced against two important constraints including the deadline for the completion of the project and the available budget (Burns and Bush, 2000).

3.6 Data sources and availability

In order to ensure that all respondents were asked the same questions, interviews were structured using a list of pre-determined questions from an interview guide. Sekaran (2000) observes that structured interviews are used when it is known from the beginning what information is needed. The aim of each question must be understood in order to recognise a significant result. While this interview technique is bound by pre-determined questions, room was allowed for additional comments and informal discussions. A prompt card was used in order to ask certain questions.

Apart from one telephone interview, interviews were conducted by the author at the respondent's place of work. For ease of data analysis, interviews were tape recorded and were transposed into interview notes where possible. Several respondents were later contacted by telephone in order to clarify issues and to be asked follow up questions.

3.7 Method of data collection

Data collected from the interview process included: a) the type of marketing metrics used by respondents; b) the personnel in the organisation who use them including whether they are used by top management such as the board; and c) the value placed on them in the assessment of overall business performance and strategic decision making.

Information on metrics collected was based on the most commonly collected marketing metrics found in a study of UK firms by Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999). This includes six major marketing metric categories, including nineteen individual metrics. Analysis also involved a seventh category of market share as this is considered an important category, as well as two additional metrics. Metrics collected included brand equity and awareness measures, customer satisfaction, loyalty, retention, perceived quality, market share, relative price and new product development. Companies were also asked if they collected any additional indicators.

Asking questions around particular metric categories gave the interview process greater structure and focus. Miles and Huberman (1994) suggest that designing a qualitative questionnaire based around the literature is a useful way to both collect and analyse data.

An evaluation of the use of marketing measurement systems including their role in business performance systems such as a balanced scorecard and key performance indicators was also assessed.

In order for the researcher to be well informed and have a good understanding of the company, it is important that background company data be studied prior to the interview process (Sekaran, 2000). This gave the qualitative research a contextual focus and allowed the researcher to raise appropriate issues relating to the research questions. Background data and information on respondent companies was collected including size of firms (revenue, number of employees), and their organisational structure. Data was collected through existing or secondary data sources such as company and financial reports.

3.8 Qualitative data analysis

According to Zikmund (2000), analysis involves the use of reasoning in order to understand and interpret the data or information that has been collected during the research phase. Specifically, it involves finding consistent patterns and themes, identifying similar relationships and phrases, discovering differences and summarising findings in the research project (Miles and Huberman 1994).

Upon completion of the interview stage, data was converted in a format that made answering the research questions possible. Primarily, this process involved editing and coding the data including organising information provided by respondents into different categories under which they fell (Sekaran, 2000; Zikmund, 2000).

Categories were primarily determined by the major research questions, the types of responses received, and the key concepts developed throughout the research project. This allowed for easier analysis and evaluation of interview results including the extrapolation of common themes, patterns and conclusions and a discussion of possible explanations and propositions.

Miles and Huberman (1994) observe that qualitative data can be organised in three stages. Data reduction via summary and paraphrasing helps to focus and organise the information collected in order for final conclusions to be made. Data display involves displaying and organising the reduced data in order for conclusions to be more easily drawn. Finally, conclusion drawing and verification aids the researcher to more easily recognise patterns, flows, the order of observations and explanations. This stage assists to provide a better understanding of what has occurred during the research process.

3.9 Qualitative validity and reliability

A sound methodology adds rigour to a research study and is vital to the credibility of the projects findings (Sekaran, 2000). There are four criteria that qualitative research needs to meet in order to be judged as sound (Trochim, 2000). The criteria for judging qualitative research include: credibility, transferability, dependability and conformability. The research project attempted to meet all four criteria.

Credibility involves the need for the researcher to establish the reliability or credibility of the research results from the participant's perspective. Participants are the only ones in the position to judge the credibility of the research results as the qualitative research is undertaken through their eyes.

The transferability criteria involve the degree to which the results of the qualitative research can be applied universally or applied to other contexts or environments. The

researcher can best achieve transferability by thoroughly describing the research situation and the major assumptions behind the research.

The researcher is also responsible for describing the changes that take place within the research context and how they affect the way the research is conducted.

Conformability refers to the extent to which the research results can be confirmed or verified. This can be achieved by the researcher recording the procedures for checking the data throughout the project or another researcher can be used to check and verify the results of the data. For the purposes of this research project, this criteria was met by tape recording each interview.

In addition, in order for the research to be verified the study must be able to be replicated by another researcher. The method of data collection and other major research methodology issues are discussed in order to achieve this.

3.10 Difficulty in securing participant involvement

It was found that securing interviews was an extremely difficult process due to the confidential nature of the information being sought, the seniority of the participants approached and their time constraints. This affected the total number of interviews conducted. In order to overcome this difficulty, a snowball sampling technique was used.

3.11 Conclusion

This section provided a description of the methodology that was used in the research project. This included issues such as data collection methods, sample selection procedures, an evaluation of the qualitative research methodology and the validity and reliability criteria that needs to be met in order for the methodology to be judged sound. The difficulty encountered in securing an adequate number of interviews was also discussed. The following chapter will provide the results and analysis of the primary data collected for each research objective outlined in chapter one.

4 DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an analysis and presentation of the primary data collected during the in-depth interview phase. The data is organised and discussed using the four research questions outlined in the introduction. Specifically, the type of marketing metrics that companies use to assess their marketing performance is considered, including the use of marketing metrics by the board and senior management. Respondents were also asked if they are satisfied with their marketing performance measurement systems and areas that required improvement. The analysis presented in this chapter helps lay the groundwork to make conclusions and implications for each research question that will be presented in chapter five.

4.2 Data analysis for each research question

RQ1: What types of marketing metrics do Australian companies use to assess their marketing performance?

Key marketing metrics

It was found that the seven metric categories and the twenty-three individual metrics listed on the prompt card provided a good description of the types of marketing metrics that companies generally collected, with several companies collecting all twenty three individual metrics listed on the prompt card. The category relating to trade customer was not relevant to companies that did not have wholesale or retail relationships.

Interviews found that respondents collected most indicators when prompted. The metrics collected by respondents are shown in Appendix 1.

Financial metrics including sales, profitability and Return on Investment (ROI) were clearly the most common category used to measure marketing performance, with all respondents interviewed collecting these metrics. They were also reviewed the most frequently.

Popular metrics mentioned by respondents included: customer loyalty and retention, brand awareness, brand/product knowledge, customer satisfaction, market share and relevance to consumer. The most common metrics collected by respondents are summarised in table 4.1.

Table 4.1. Key Marketing Metrics collected by respondents

- Financial (Sales, profit, margin)
- Customer loyalty/retention
- Brand awareness
- Brand/product knowledge
- Market share
- Relevance to consumer
- Perceived quality
- Customer satisfaction
- Number of new customers
- Total number of customers
- Relative price
- Relative perceived quality

Source: Developed from in depth interviews

While external comparison varied across respondents, interviews found that companies benchmarked their marketing performance against external competitors where possible. Companies indicated that comparing metrics against external competitor performance was important in order to gain a true indication of marketing performance.

Collection of additional marketing metrics and measures

Interviews found that respondents collect a number of metrics that were not listed on the prompt card. Measures that assessed brand reputation and health, including likeability and personality traits such as trust were frequently mentioned by respondents. For example, one respondent assessed corporate brand on factors including competence and cleverness. Respondents also listed detailed awareness measures, consideration and share of wallet metrics. Additional metrics collected by respondents are listed in Appendix 1.

While the seven categories were found to be useful in prompting respondents, companies did not necessarily group categories or define the metrics in this way. For

example, some respondents reported metrics under the category of brand health or brand reputation.

While the majority of metrics collected were quantitative, it was found that respondents also collected qualitative measures including a number of brand image statements. This included attitudinal measures of brand perceptions such as likeability, trust, customer satisfaction, range and quality of products and service, vision, leadership, innovation and corporate responsibility.

Companies also used proxy or surrogate indicators as marketing metrics. For example, several organisations used the number of complaints lodged via a customer enquires hot line as an indicator of customer satisfaction.

Measuring ROI and marketing expenditure

Respondent companies closely monitored marketing expenditure and the performance of individual marketing programs. Where possible, companies measured the financial contribution of promotional and advertising expenditure using an ROI. These included advertising campaigns, customer loyalty programs, sponsorship campaigns and new product launches. Respondents that did not measure an ROI indicated an interest to do so in the future.

The development of an ROI on marketing expenditure was considered an important issue in marketing and was reflected in the following comment:

'An ROI on marketing would be the Holy Grail.'

The measurement of consumer behaviour and advertising effectiveness was considered complex and respondents indicated that some activities such as sponsorship campaigns were much easier to measure.

Several respondents suggested they were developing a number of models to measure the effectiveness of marketing and advertising campaigns, including awareness and brand equity models.

Additional findings

Interviews also revealed the following:

- Definitions of individual marketing metrics were not always consistent across companies interviewed. This was especially found in soft data such as the consumer intermediate category (thoughts and feelings).
- The measurement of marketing performance varied across company and industry. Competition was found to be a major driver of the development of marketing metrics. For example, in the highly competitive fast moving consumer goods Industry, the measurement of marketing performance was well developed and the number of metrics collected was vast and very detailed. Consumer intermediate and innovation metrics were highly developed in competitive industries. In comparison, in deregulated industries or industries where competition is developing, marketing metrics were not as highly developed.
- Respondent companies did not use a consistent term when referring to the brand as a marketing asset. Companies interchanged between terms including brand equity, brand health or brand reputation. The term used was influenced by both the situation in which it was used as well as the culture of the organisation.
- Although it was recognised there was a greater need for it, companies did not generally practise brand valuation.
- The collection and analysis of marketing metrics and intelligence was a coordinated process usually organised by a centralised function such as marketing, customer insights or a knowledge team. These functions played a leading role in both coordinating information across business units including sales, finance, operations and manufacturing and presenting findings to senior management.
- Frequency of marketing metrics reviewed ranged between a daily, weekly, monthly, half yearly or annual basis. Top line measures including brand awareness, customer satisfaction and market share were reviewed more frequently by senior management.
- Metrics considered not to change greatly over time were reviewed by several respondents on an ad hoc or annual basis.

RQ2: Is a review of marketing performance, including a review of marketing metrics undertaken by the board of directors and senior executive management such as the CEO?***Board of Directors***

Interviews revealed that the board of directors does not place a large focus on marketing metrics when assessing company and marketing performance. Boards seem to place a larger emphasis on financial measures such as sales and profitability, while they are reviewed the most frequently. Additionally, marketing metrics did not appear to be integrated with financial measures. While in some cases key marketing metrics are reviewed at board level, boards do not generally undertake a review of marketing performance.

It was also found that some boards only reviewed marketing metrics on an ad hoc basis or if a particular need arose such as deterioration in financial performance or a brand management ‘crisis’.

The board’s focus on financial metrics was shown by the following comments:

‘Boards want to know how much money we’re making and that’s the bottom line.’

‘Customer satisfaction falls way behind financial implications at a board level.’

‘Most of the marketing metrics are exception reporting.’

Respondents suggested that a presentation of a range of marketing metrics was considered too detailed to be tabled at board level with respondents making the following comments:

‘While the Managing Director of the brand is interested in marketing metrics, he necessarily does not have to tell the CEO (who sits on the board) what’s happening on a regular basis unless there is an issue.’

'A board would say, "We employ a CEO of a company, who employ senior management and they should be resolving those issues." '

Interviews found that it was not common for boards to review consumer behaviour metrics. Marketing metrics including customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, perceived quality, brand product knowledge and number of new consumers were generally not reviewed at board level.

It was also revealed that boards do not review marketing activities such as marketing expenditure and an ROI on specific marketing activities on a regular basis. Additionally, it was not common for the valuation of key marketing assets such as key customer relationships and customer loyalty programs to be reviewed by boards.

Respondents' answers revealed that the most common marketing metrics reviewed at board level were market share and brand awareness. Brand health and innovation metrics were also popular at board level.

However, marketing metrics appear to be becoming more important with respondents reporting that they were developing a range of new marketing measures and metric systems including marketing metric reports, brand health scorecards, brand audits and a marketing dashboard specifically to be reviewed at board level.

Interviews also revealed that several boards were more focused on marketing performance. Marketing focused boards closely monitored marketing performance and regularly reviewed a number of marketing metrics at monthly board meetings. Metrics including market share, brand and advertising awareness, marketing expenditure, consideration and trial rates were regularly reviewed by the board.

It was also found that marketing focused boards reviewed the valuation and growth of key marketing assets including economic profit by brand, key customer relationships, value by customer segment, product category and channel and customer loyalty programs.

CEO and Senior Executive Management

Interviews found that individual marketing metrics reach Senior Executive Management including the Chief Executive Officer (CEO) and the Managing Director. While the organisational structure of each company differed across respondents, Senior Executive Management can be defined as key executive staff including the CEO, Managing Directors of individual brands and divisions and General Managers of business units. It also includes the Chief Financial Officer and members of an Executive Management or operating committee who are responsible for the day to day running of the organisation including strategic direction and brand management.

It was generally found that the more senior the personnel in the organisation, the less detail they would see on marketing performance and marketing metrics. While the number of metrics reviewed at senior level differed from company to company, it was common for key marketing metrics such as brand awareness, customer satisfaction and market share to be reviewed at senior management level. Marketing expenditure and an ROI were also regularly reviewed by senior management.

The type of organisation and its structure also appeared to influence the range and detail of marketing metrics reviewed by senior management. For example, in corporations that contained a number of brands, a full range of marketing metrics would reach a level as high as the managing director of the individual brand. The CEO would generally see aggregated metrics for the master brand and key metrics for the sub brands.

Marketing metrics were also consistently seen and reviewed by senior marketing personnel including the most senior marketing officer in the organisation including group marketing heads, marketing directors and marketing general managers who as part of their role regularly reviewed and were naturally interested in marketing performance.

It was found that metrics were also viewed across marketing, sales and customer personnel including brand, product and sales managers. In some cases marketing

metrics including customer satisfaction would reach front line staff such as customer service.

RQ3: What value does senior management place on marketing metrics in the assessment of overall business performance and are they synchronised with the firm's business objectives?

Respondents were questioned in order to determine the following: 1) the value that senior management places on marketing metrics in measuring overall business performance in relation to financial measures; and 2) whether or not marketing metrics are aligned to corporate objectives and business strategy (i.e. do the metrics fit the objectives?)

Financial metrics were regarded by senior management as being the most important in the evaluation of overall business and marketing performance. However, senior management appeared to place a high value on key marketing metrics such as brand awareness, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in measuring and providing an understanding into the drivers behind overall business performance. Metrics were seen to provide senior management with a critical insight into consumers, competitors and markets and were therefore considered a key source of competitive advantage.

'Metrics contribute to where the business is today.'

'The more information and tools you have, the better you can drive the ship.'

Respondents recognised there was beginning to become a greater recognition of the role of marketing metrics in assessing company and marketing performance, with a number of companies developing a variety of new marketing metric systems and scorecards for use at board and senior management level as mentioned previously. It was expected that metrics such as brand awareness and customer satisfaction would receive more attention in the future which was shown by the following statement.

'Boards will become more comfortable with measures such as brand measures, customers satisfaction, customer churn.'

Marketing metrics as leading indicators of business health

While it was acknowledged that financial measures were considered the most important metrics when analysing both marketing and overall business performance, marketing metrics were recognised as having a critical role to play as lead indicators of corporate performance with companies stating:

‘Senior management like to look at lead indicators of how the business is performing such as, “What are our consumers thinking about our brands?”’

‘Financials are a static measure, historical view, but what are the input measures that are the recipe for success?’

‘Marketing metrics are critical because the results could be disastrous if you don’t get it right.’

However, some respondents suggested that there was not a great emphasis on marketing metrics in their organisations.

‘We are more financial driven than marketing driven.’

‘When you’re struggling from week to week, marketing metrics just don’t come into it.’

Link between marketing metrics to company performance and the bottom line

Respondents strongly believed that there was a strong link between marketing outputs including customer satisfaction and brand awareness to a company’s financial performance. The importance of measuring marketing performance and its influence on overall business performance was shown in the following statements:

‘If you’re not progressing in terms of brand reputation, client relationships and the value of those relationships, then you’re probably not making enough progress.’

'If we get all these things right, they would unequivocally have an impact on the financial metrics.'

'Revenue can be a very seductive thing, but it may not be the right answer'.

'Financials are very much an output measure. If you get your act together in terms of customer satisfaction and perceived quality, you will actually deliver good financials.'

Marketing's wider role in measuring business performance

Marketing was so well regarded in several firms that it was given a wider role to play in measuring business performance. For example, in one particular firm, marketing was given the responsibility of measuring non-marketing related activities such as a return on an IT investment project with respondents stating:

'We try to pass our opinion in a structured, objective and analytical type way based around information and data.'

'Other parts of this organisation are looking to marketing to provide insight.'

While it was recognised that marketing assets such as brand reputation and long term customer relationships were critical to an organisation's financial health, senior management have traditionally viewed them as intangibles. Metrics were seen as having an important role to play in communicating the value of marketing assets to senior levels of the organisation.

Marketing metrics are synchronised with corporate objectives

Answers to this issue revealed that marketing measures were clearly aligned with company's overall business objectives and corporate strategy. Key marketing metrics play a role in measuring the progress of both marketing and corporate strategy via the business planning process. Metrics including brand reputation and health, awareness and customer satisfaction were considered critical in driving consumer adoption. Perceived quality and market share were also considered key strategic objectives.

The linking of metrics to a firm's strategy and objectives was revealed in three ways. Firstly, key marketing objectives for sales, profit, customer satisfaction, loyalty, brand awareness and market share were found to be overall business objectives and were set as explicit targets in marketing and broader business plans.

Additionally, it was found that many marketing objectives were used as Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for business units and senior personnel. Common marketing KPI included: sales, ROI, gross margins, customer satisfaction, brand awareness, customer retention and acquisitions, total number of customers, market share and innovation targets. In some cases, KPI were also used to assess the performance of advertising agencies.

Finally, as customer focused and modern marketing organisations, respondents were concerned about issues such as customer satisfaction and therefore showed interest in measuring it.

It was found that marketing metrics were monitored over time and compared to previous period and budget, and where possible, external competitor performance. Several respondents also established marketing targets against their competitors. For multi branded corporations, targets were established for each individual brand. Comments highlighting the importance of marketing metrics to business strategy included:

'Metrics are directly aligned to strategy and the direction we want to go in.'

'There is no use in having a strategy if you can't measure it.'

'Customer satisfaction, loyalty and awareness are written into business plans and need to be at a certain level at a certain time. If they are not, issues such as media exposure need to be addressed.'

'We set KPIs around brand performance measures including number of consumers, awareness and the role of advertising.'

Marketing's role in creating a company vision

Respondents also felt that marketing and by extension, marketing metrics had a key role to play in creating a company vision and developing new growth opportunities in areas such as customer acquisitions and innovation. This point was highlighted by the following comments:

'How do we increase consumption patterns, that's driving your metrics therefore driving your business opportunities and corporate strategy?'

'Investment analysts are beginning to ask about innovation, pricing and driving growth in the future.'

Several respondents attributed both marketing and marketing metrics as playing leading roles in transforming their companies from production to leading marketing and customer focused organisations.

'The CEO wants to take us from an engineering to a marketing led company.'

Respondents believed that as competition and markets further developed, companies would become more marketing focused and marketing metrics would play a greater role.

RQ4: Are companies satisfied in the way their marketing performance is measured and are there any areas that require improvement?

Interviews found that while respondents were generally satisfied with the way marketing was measured, they did not consider themselves to adhere to best practice when compared to companies in general. Respondents felt that other companies and industries had better information and more effective metrics.

Respondents also discussed areas that needed greater improvement and these are listed in table 4.2.

Table 4.2. Key improvements mentioned by respondents

- Develop link between marketing metrics and financial performance
- Improve measurement of ROI of marketing and advertising campaigns
- Greater focus of marketing metrics by board and senior management
- Consolidation of metrics required
- Consistency of definitions and systems across discipline

Source: Developed from in-depth interviews

Greater focus of marketing and marketing performance needed at board and senior level.

While respondents believed that top level management were marketing and customer focused, a greater focus on marketing metrics was needed by both the board and senior management. A respondent said that this could be achieved by:

‘A marketing scorecard (which) should appear in every monthly board paper of how marketing is performing.’

Several respondents believed that some boards were too focused on bottom line results and a greater balance between financial and non-financial metrics was required. One respondent suggested that this was evident at public announcements of company results, which in many cases focused on financial results only. Companies needed to do a better job of communicating key strategic drivers and new growth opportunities to investors, consumers and employees through greater use of non-financial indicators such as marketing metrics. Marketing was seen as having a key role to play in developing new growth opportunities. The following comment suggests that the board and senior management need to communicate marketing performance to stakeholders:

‘You rarely as a consumer or investment community hear when financial results are announced, what happened to drive that result and what is happening in the future.’

Marketing needs to become more financially accountable

Respondents believed that in order for marketing issues to gain greater attention and credibility at top-level management, marketing needs to become more financially accountable and demonstrate what its activities contribute to the organisation.

Establishing a link between marketing metrics and financial measures would also provide marketing with a greater role in corporate strategy.

Marketing's lack of financial accountability and its inability to establish a more than implicit relationship to sales and profitability, influence the way it is seen by senior management:

'Marketing tends to be seen as flaky and not process driven...and struggles to be coordinated and disciplined in a metric driven manner.'

'Senior management at CEO and board level need to view marketing not as a cost factor but as an investment factor. In most instances as part of profit and loss, it is considered a cost and not an investment, which tells you something about the mindset of the organisation.'

Respondents suggested that marketing needs to develop measures and systems that were robust, understandable and appropriate for senior management and board level. Respondents believed that in order for marketing to gain greater influence at board level and be considered a methodical discipline, it must develop sophisticated models that link metrics such as brand awareness and customer satisfaction to financial results such as revenue and shareholder value.

'You need to have relevant language for senior and board level.'

'If there is no process of directly linking brand health to the bottom line, what's the point?'

'Unless there is an integrated process that says that we need to understand as an organisation at a board level the metrics that are being generated from your brand

awareness tracking system because it plays a key role in implementing decisions that we make at a board level, it does not make it on their radar screens other than on an ad hoc basis.'

Respondents felt that marketing has a responsibility to justify its expenditure and what it contributes to the firm by providing better financial information. While marketing was increasingly viewed as an investment rather than an expense, improvement was needed in the measurement of an ROI of promotional and advertising expenditure. It was widely felt that this was a critical issue facing marketing. Respondents also suggested that this would also serve to make media and advertising agencies more accountable.

While respondents acknowledged that measuring consumer behaviour and the effectiveness of advertising awareness is difficult, it was crucial that marketing becomes better at measuring the financial returns of marketing activities by:

'Linking the marketing measures, the soft stuff, the awareness the perception to the hard stuff, the numbers which influence the balance sheet.'

'What is the sales effect if we increase brand awareness from x to y and what is the time effect for that occurring?'

Greater marketing representation required at senior management and board level

In several organisations, the marketing backgrounds of top management seemed to influence the use and understanding of marketing metrics. It was generally found that if the CEO or Managing Director had a background in marketing, there was a greater appreciation of the importance of measuring marketing performance and marketing issues, such as brands, new growth opportunities and competition.

The importance of marketing's influence at board and senior level was shown by the following statement:

'Our Managing Director is consumer behaviour obsessed and asks how strongly we are linked to our consumers, how strong are our consumer relationships, and how can we improve our customer relationships.'

Several respondents felt that the lack of marketing expertise of senior management meant they had a difficulty in understanding strategic marketing issues and evaluating marketing's contribution to the organisation:

'The absence of a senior marketing person at a high level makes it more difficult.'

'The old guys are doing it because that's the way they have always done it.'

'They know it's important (the board), but they don't know why.'

One respondent suggested that one solution was to draw board members from a number of disciplines including marketing:

'It makes sense to have a board that's got some cross process skills and not just the bean counters.'

Greater consolidation and focus

Several respondents also felt that marketing was guilty of providing too much information and in some cases, reducing the number of metrics was seen as necessary. Focusing on metrics that are relevant to current business strategy and have an impact on the balance sheet was cited as a major challenge with respondents stating:

'Marketers are guilty of measuring too much.'

'The challenge is having the vital few, the top four to five that will have an eighty percent impact on your result.'

'We can measure anything, but are we measuring the right things?'

Respondents mentioned that there was a greater need to develop a range of new and more sophisticated metrics in order to reflect consumer and technological changes and improve marketing and business performance. Respondents listed several areas where metrics are required be developed. These included measures that identified factors behind customer churn, share of situation and new product innovation metrics.

Respondents believed improvements were also necessary in the analysis of customer relationship data including data mining, which could lead to greater understanding of consumer behaviour allowing companies to provide better products and services for their customers.

Respondents also believed an improvement was required in the collection and analysis of 'softer' measures such as customer satisfaction, loyalty and retention.

Achieving a consistent approach in developing the necessary measurement tools and models across the marketing discipline was cited as a common concern among respondents. This included using consistent systems, methods and definitions of metrics across the entire discipline.

4.5 Conclusion

In depth interviews revealed that while the measurement of marketing performance varied across companies and industries, respondents measured their marketing performance using a wide range of marketing metrics. It was found that the measurement of marketing was well developed and was considered a serious business issue.

However, it was generally found that there was no formal system for assessing marketing metrics or the performance of the brand as part of an overall business performance management system. Additionally, marketing metrics were not integrated with financial metrics.

Financial metrics were the most frequently used and were considered the most important means of evaluating marketing performance. Key marketing metrics were found to be customer loyalty/retention, brand awareness, brand product knowledge and market share. Companies also routinely collected information on marketing expenditure and where possible, measured the financial return of marketing programs using an ROI.

Respondents also collected a number of metrics not listed on the interview prompt card including a number of awareness and brand health metrics.

Interviews revealed that while senior executive management including the CEO review individual marketing metrics, the board of directors do not receive a comprehensive view of marketing performance. According to Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999), a review of marketing performance involves a routine system of evaluating the performance of the brand over time, benchmarked against external (competitor) and internal (marketing and business plans) performance, accordingly adjusted by any gain or loss in a firm's main marketing asset. This includes a review of key marketing metrics, marketing programs and expenditure and a valuation of marketing assets. Brand valuation was found not to be widely practised by firms.

While in some cases boards would review key marketing metrics, metrics such as customer satisfaction, loyalty and perceived quality often did not reach board level.

Common marketing metrics that reached the board included brand awareness, market share and innovation measures.

While financial metrics were clearly seen by respondents as the most important category, respondents acknowledged the increasing importance of marketing metrics in assessing business performance and providing vital customer and competitor insight. Metrics were also seen as leading indicators of sales and profitability.

Marketing metrics were found to play a key role in measuring the performance of marketing and corporate strategy. Metrics were set as targets in marketing plans,

which were aligned and fed directly into corporate plans. Metrics were also compared against last period and externally benchmarked. Key performance indicators include brand awareness, customer satisfaction and market share.

While respondents were satisfied with how marketing performance was measured, they felt that other industries and companies had better metrics and tools for measuring marketing performance.

Respondents also listed a number of areas that needed improvement. Firstly, boards and senior management needed to find a balance between the use of financial and non-financial metrics. Respondents felt that there needed to be a greater focus on marketing metrics at top management level. Respondents also believed that marketing needed to improve its financial accountability by developing a robust relationship between marketing metrics and financial performance. Linking metrics to financial measures such as profitability and shareholder value was seen as a critical marketing issue, which would give marketing greater credibility and relevance at board and CEO level. Marketing also needed to justify its expenditure by producing more accurate financial information on its advertising and promotional programs including developing better ROI models. Finally, it was revealed that some companies suffer from data overload. Focusing on the key metrics that were relevant to both current business strategy and financial performance was considered essential.

The conclusions for each research question and their implications for the theory and practice presented in the literature review are discussed in the final chapter.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter a conclusion is reached on the major research objective including conclusions for the four individual research questions. Implications for both Australian companies and the marketing discipline are discussed, including recommendations for further research areas. The limitations of the project are also discussed.

5.2 Conclusions of the major research objective

The study found that measuring marketing performance is highly developed across respondents. The individual metrics listed on the prompt card were a good description of the types of metrics companies collected. While the importance of marketing metrics was recognised in the assessment of business and marketing performance, it appears they are not integrated with financial metrics as part of an overall business performance management system such as a balanced scorecard.

Additionally, firms only met two out of the three criteria listed by Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) that are necessary to successfully measure marketing performance (comparison with both internal and external benchmarks, accordingly adjusted by changes in the gain or loss in a company's brand equity). Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) found that only 20 percent of firms in the UK met all three criteria. While respondents in this study met the first two criteria, the valuation of brand equity was not widely practised. This is consistent with findings in both the United Kingdom (Smith, 2001) and in Australia (Lloyd, 2001).

While key marketing metrics reach some boards, a comprehensive and formal review of marketing performance does not occur at top level management. It appears that marketing performance is not regularly reviewed at board level.

Marketing metrics were found to be synchronised with respondent firms' overall objectives and business strategies via marketing and business planning. However, financial metrics were likely to dominate both marketing and broader corporate plans.

Respondents were generally satisfied with their marketing performance practices, however they felt that other companies and industries had better systems and metrics. Respondents discussed several areas that required improvement. Conclusions regarding each research question are discussed below.

5.3 Conclusions about each research question

RQ1: What types of marketing metrics do Australian companies currently use to assess their marketing performance?

Companies involved in the study use a wide range of marketing metrics in order to measure their marketing performance. The nineteen individual metrics and six metric categories identified by Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) were a good description of the metrics collected. While the categories provided a useful way to describe the metrics, respondents did not always group or define metrics in this way. For example, it was common for consumer intermediate metrics to be grouped under brand health or reputation.

Marketing metrics appear to be becoming more important at top level management with respondents developing new marketing metrics systems and brand health scorecards, specifically to be viewed by the board of directors.

The study found that companies place a greater emphasis on financial metrics when measuring marketing performance. This is consistent with the studies by Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) and Styles (2000). Financial metrics were also more regularly assessed and were considered the most valuable.

Key marketing metrics used by companies were customer loyalty/retention, brand awareness, brand product knowledge and market share. This is similar to findings by

Ambler (2000) regarding the most common marketing metrics used by companies in the UK.

The monitoring of marketing expenditure and the measurement of an ROI of marketing programs was found to be common practice. However, in some cases the reporting of an ROI was not always possible because of the difficulty found in measuring consumer behaviour and advertising effectiveness.

This study also found that companies collect a number of additional metrics in order to measure their marketing performance. For example, companies collected a number of metrics not listed on the prompt card such as economic profit by brand and a number of different awareness funnels. According to Ambler (2000), many of these metrics were collected but did not make the final survey listed in the literature review.

RQ2: Is a review of marketing performance, including a review of marketing metrics undertaken by the board of directors and senior executive management such as the CEO?

The study found that boards do not receive a comprehensive view of marketing performance, including a review of marketing metrics when assessing company performance.

While it was observed that key marketing metrics reach some boards, it was not common for marketing performance to be comprehensively reviewed at board level. Brand valuation was not widely practised by firms. This was consistent with findings by Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999).

In many cases, metrics such as customer satisfaction, loyalty and perceived quality do not appear to reach board level on a regular basis. This is similar to a finding by Styles (2000) that the use of customer based marketing metrics by Australian boards is not common practice.

However, the boards of several marketing focused organisations closely monitored key metrics against key performance indicators or strategic milestones. Notably, this was found to be the exception rather than the norm.

Popular metrics reviewed by the board in this study include brand awareness and market share, number of new products and revenue of new products.

The study found individual marketing metrics are reviewed by senior executive management including the CEO and Managing Director. Marketing expenditure including the assessment of marketing activities is also reviewed at senior management level. This study is similar to the finding by Ambler (2001) that individual metrics reach CEO and top executive level.

RQ3: What value does senior management place on marketing metrics in the assessment of overall business performance and are they synchronised with the firm's business objectives?

Respondents suggested that when assessing marketing and business performance, the board of directors and senior management place a higher importance on financial measures. Marketing metrics are not commonly integrated with financial measures as part of an overall business performance management system.

As expected, financial measures were also more frequently reviewed by the board than any other metrics. The findings were consistent with two studies conducted by Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) and Styles (2000).

Some respondents felt that because marketing metrics provide senior management with critical information on consumers, competition and products, they could gain a strategic edge over their competitors and therefore saw metrics as a source of competitive advantage. Marketing metrics were seen as leading indicators of business performance because of their strong relationship with financial measures such as sales and profitability.

Additionally, it appears that senior management take a greater interest in marketing performance when they have marketing backgrounds.

Marketing metrics were found to be synchronised with corporate objectives via the business planning process. Metrics are used to set objectives or targets and were seen as vital indicators of the progress of strategic goals. Metrics play key roles in marketing plans that feed into overall business strategy. They are closely monitored over time and are externally benchmarked against competitor performance. Key metrics such as brand awareness, customer satisfaction and market share are commonly used as key performance indicators.

The implication of this finding is that marketing may therefore influence corporate strategy and is consistent with a study by McKinsey and Company (Brady et al, 2000) which found that marketing was strongly linked to corporate and business unit strategic decision making.

While marketing metrics play a large part in marketing plans, they may be somewhat implicit when they reach the corporate level plan. This is because marketing plans feed into larger business plans where financial metrics play a greater role. This is consistent with Ambler's (2000) finding that financial measures such as sales, costs and profits dominate and are given greater importance than marketing metrics in marketing and corporate plans.

RQ4: Are companies satisfied in the way their marketing performance is measured and are there any areas that require improvement?

Despite their belief that other competitors and industries had better marketing measurement practices, this study found that respondents were generally satisfied with the measurement of marketing performance in their companies.

This compares to a finding by Styles (2000) that claims that the measurement of marketing effectiveness is not considered a current or future marketing challenge.

However, Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) claim that participants in their study were not satisfied with their marketing performance measurement systems because financial measures were given greater importance.

Respondents also discussed major areas that required improvement.

Firstly, boards and senior management needed to have a greater focus on marketing performance including a more regular review of marketing metrics.

It was widely acknowledged that there is a need for marketing to become more accountable by linking marketing activities to financial returns. This involves developing tools and models that link marketing metrics to financial measures that are important to the board and CEO. It was believed that this would enable marketing issues to gain a greater influence at board level. Marketing also needs to improve the measurement of an ROI on marketing programs and expenditure. This is consistent with the claim by Lehmann (2002) that there is a need to establish a quantitative link between marketing metrics to financial measures. This is considered a contemporary marketing issue with the US Marketing Science Institute recognising that marketing must be more financially accountable. It has listed marketing metrics as its top research priority for 2002 (HREF 1).

This study found that some larger companies were overwhelmed with data and had more metrics than were necessary. As this can cause confusion and lack of focus, there is a need for some companies to reduce the number of metrics and focus on metrics that fit their current business strategy. It was also identified that marketing metrics need to keep pace with consumer and market changes. Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) have suggested similar improvements.

5.4 Implications for theory and practice

In a world where fierce global competition, new technologies, demanding consumers and continuous innovation are viewed as the norm, the challenge for top management to perform is on. Marketing's role in helping organisations navigate through this rapidly changing and complex business environment is critical. The proliferation of consumer choice means companies are increasingly using marketing strategies and their brands to shape consumer preferences and create superior customer value. In order to meet these challenges, companies therefore require tools and information on customers, competitors and products that are timely and robust. The measurement of marketing performance is therefore becoming increasingly essential.

Recent corporate collapses in both Australia and the United States is driving greater corporate accountability and is placing demands on management to provide more information in the form of metrics. According to the Cap Gemini Center for Business Innovation (2002), the US Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) may make disclosure of non-financial information mandatory. Today, there is greater pressure on all areas of a company, including marketing to become more financially accountable and demonstrate the effectiveness of its activities. Marketing needs to provide better financial information and show what it contributes to a firm's bottom line.

The drive for increased accountability means that a greater balance between financial and non-financial indicators is required at both board and senior management level. Senior management and the board need to show a greater interest in marketing performance including a regular review of marketing metrics. While companies are slowly beginning to appreciate the importance of marketing metrics and are developing systems for top level management, too often than not, customer satisfaction and brand health metrics fail to reach board level.

Key marketing metrics including a return on investment of marketing expenditure should also be reported at board level. Brand valuation including the economic profit of brands and the valuation of marketing assets such as key customer relationships should also be reviewed regularly by the board and the CEO.

In today's competitive environment, a regularly review of marketing performance including marketing metrics should be mandatory practice for all boards and senior management. This may involve a review of a marketing scorecard or dashboard on a regular basis that provides a snapshot of marketing performance. The scorecard should focus on 5-10 appropriate metrics that are easily understood and are clearly linked to the firm's financial measures. Metrics also need to be high level (i.e. seen by senior level management), necessary, sufficient, unambiguous (consistency across the discipline) and predictive as suggested by Kokkinaki and Abmler (1999). Where possible, metrics should always be externally benchmarked against competitor performance.

Metrics should also be clearly integrated with marketing and corporate strategy, allowing the evaluation of the progress of strategic objectives. This would enable marketing activities to be regularly reviewed at board level, improving its accountability and demonstrating to senior management how it contributes to corporate goals.

In order to measure its success, new marketing metrics should be developed when there are changes in strategy. Metrics should also reflect consumer, product and technological changes.

For marketing metrics to become part of a routine performance management system and become more relevant at senior management and board level, marketing's financial contribution to the organisation requires a more formal assessment process. Marketing metrics must be formally integrated with financial measures such as profitability, sales and an ROI by each brand. Methodical and systematic models that link metrics to bottom line results should be developed.

In order for marketing to be taken more seriously by the CEO and the board, the marketing discipline needs to develop greater analytical rigour in the measurement of its productivity and provide a link between a firm's marketing activities and its financial performance. Marketing metrics such as brand awareness, customer satisfaction and market share should be linked with financial metrics that senior management care about including profitability and shareholder value.

Kokkinaki and Ambler (1999) claim that a successful assessment of marketing performance requires that companies adjust short-term measures by the gain or loss in brand equity during the period under review. For many companies, brand equity is their most valuable asset, however, brand valuation in this study was found not to be common practice. According to Lloyd (2001), only 12 out of the 43 biggest Australian companies include the value of their brands in their company accounts. Ambler (2001) suggests that companies need to measure the value of their brands so they can know if they are living off accumulated assets of the past or whether they are building assets for the future. In order to effectively measure marketing performance, Australian companies should measure and report the value of their brands.

Better methods of measuring the ROI of marketing programs, including developing better valuation models of promotional and advertising expenditure is also necessary.

Furthermore, boards need to have a better understanding of marketing strategy. While short-term financial results are important, boards need to appreciate how marketing's brand building activities can create greater customer and shareholder value. A greater representation of marketing at CEO and board level may help. This study found that marketing issues appeared to be given greater importance when the CEO or Managing Director had a background in marketing.

The recent publicity on the performance of Australian Company directors has led some to question the role of the board of directors. According to Don Argus, chairman of BHP Billiton and Brambles:

“And the one thing that boards don't do well is they don't get involved with the strategy setting, and they don't understand the risks that are associated with the delivery of the strategy... The first thing you have to do is understand the strategy. I have a view that if a board member can't articulate the strategy of a company, then he really should not be on the board. I feel pretty strongly about that” (Jimenez 2002, p. 32).

According to Ambler (2000), metrics can play a key role in communicating and gaining commitment to goals, while Davidson (1999) claims that this can make companies more customer and future driven. This is important for activities that involve new growth opportunities such as product innovation and the cultivation of new markets. Doyle (2001) suggests customer awareness, customer satisfaction and market share are not goals in their own right, but strategies to create greater shareholder value. Both senior management and some marketers require a greater appreciation of this.

Marketing needs to develop a greater level of professionalism in the area of marketing metrics. A set of standardised marketing metrics and language should be developed that is applicable across industries. Standardisation should be similar to other

disciplines such as accounting. Marketing educators should play a role in addressing this area.

Finally, the establishment of autonomous knowledge management or customer insight teams who are responsible for collecting, managing and analysing marketing metrics and reporting systems should become standard practice in all market driven organisations. Teams should be independent from marketing, sales and finance have the ability to report directly to the CEO and the board. This would ensure that marketing is seen as a subjective voice in the organisation and is aligned to the company's overall strategy.

The role of intangible assets such as brand equity, reputation and innovation are taking on greater importance in today's economy; and is driving the greater use of traditional non-financial measures, including marketing metrics. The Cap Gemini Center for Business Innovation (2001) claims that the current system for measuring and disclosing corporate performance - developed over 500 years ago - is no longer adequate. Top executive management need to create reporting systems that provides insights on how their organisations create value for customers, employees and investors. Marketing metrics have an important role to play in this emerging business trend.

5.5 Limitations

A limitation of this study was that respondents were not asked how marketing metrics were used. This study focused only on identifying those that were used.

Correlation was not determined among the different metrics, a firm's marketing orientation and company performance.

In some cases, it was only possible to gain a view of the use of metrics at the individual brand level and not the corporate or master brand level.

Finally, the study may have suffered from bias because respondents in the project were marketing personnel, not company directors or senior management themselves.

Responses may have also differed if participants were from other disciplines such as finance.

5.6 Future research

A number of research studies are recommended to further explore this topic. As this study only provided exploratory qualitative research, analytical generalisations cannot be attributed to the whole population. It is therefore recommended that a quantitative study of the use of marketing metrics by Australian firms be conducted. This will help to confirm the findings in this study. This should also seek to determine whether participants are satisfied with their marketing measurement practices.

Additionally, a study involving in depth interviews of senior management and company directors in order to ascertain the use and value of marketing metrics in corporate strategic decision making is recommended. The influence of the marketing backgrounds of top management might also be considered. Research on how other disciplines such as finance perceive marketing metrics could also be conducted.

A study on how metrics are chosen and developed should be undertaken. This could include how metrics are used and tailored to company strategy, their relationship to tactics, including how they are communicated throughout the organisation. Issues that influence their development such as a firm's culture could also be considered.

Also, research on individual metric categories could provide useful and specific information for that category. Research could include the development of new metrics, assessing the valuation of customers (e.g. customer lifetime value), brands and the measurement of innovation.

Further research is required to determine the predictiveness of marketing metrics and the effects of a firm's marketing efforts on its financial performance. This would involve establishing quantitative links between marketing metrics including brand awareness and customer satisfaction to financial performance and shareholder value. A study should also be conducted that improves the measurement of marketing ROI programs, including providing a link of marketing activities including promotions and

advertising to financial measures. Understanding the relationship between strategic marketing decisions and shareholder value could also provide useful information.

Finally, research establishing a relationship between the use of marketing metrics and the financial performance of Australian firms should be conducted.

The marketing discipline needs to take responsibility for many of these research areas. There is evidence that this is happening. In 1998 and 2002, "Assessing marketing productivity and marketing metrics" was ranked as the leading research priority by the Marketing Science Institute. In October 2002, the Marketing Science Institute held a major conference called: "Measuring Marketing Productivity: Linking Marketing to Financial Returns" ([HREF 1](#)).

APPENDIX 1: DATA COLLECTED FROM RESPONDENTS

Marketing Metrics Collected by Respondents												
	Respondents' scores											
	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10	R11	R12
Consumer Intermediate												
Brand Awareness	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Perceived quality	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓
Consumer satisfaction		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Relevance to consumer	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Perceived differentiation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓
Brand/ product knowledge	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Consumer Behaviour												
Number of new consumers		✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Customer loyalty/ retention	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Conversions		✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Market												
Market share	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Total number of customers	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Trade Customer												
Distribution/Availability	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
Customer satisfaction	✓	✓	✓				✓			✓	✓	✓
Number of complaints	✓	✓	✓				✓			✓	✓	✓
Relative to competitor												
Relative consumer satisfaction	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓
Relative perceived quality	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
Relative price	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	
Innovation												
Number of new products	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Revenue of new products	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Margin of new products	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Financial												
Sales	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Gross margins	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Profitability (ROI)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
✓ Metric collected by respondent												
☐ Metric regularly reviewed by Board of Directors												
	Source: Developed from in depth interviews											

Additional metrics collected by respondents

Metrics category	Metrics
Consumer Intermediate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Brand reputation and health ▪ Brand dimensions and attributes e.g. likeability, personalty traits etc. ▪ Different stages of awareness (i.e. awareness funnels) ▪ Consideration measures ▪ Conversions and trial rates ▪ Advertising awareness and tracking ▪ Product quality and durability ▪ Perceived value ▪ Perceived price
Consumer Behaviour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Customer satisfaction by channel ▪ Consumer complaints ▪ Future buying intentions
Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Share of wallet ▪ Weight of purchase ▪ Frequency of purchase ▪ Market share by customer (behaviour and situation), product, channel and geographic segment ▪ Future market share
Relative to competitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All metrics compared to competitor where possible
Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Perceived innovation ▪ Speed to market
Financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economic profit by brand ▪ Return on shareholder equity

Source: Developed from in depth interviews

APPENDIX 2: INTERVIEW GUIDE

Questions

1. Looking at the table, what marketing performance measures does your company collect?
2. Are there any other measures that your company collects that are considered to be marketing measures?
3. Which personnel in the organisation review these measures (e.g. Board/senior management, middle management, all levels of the organisation)?
4. What marketing performance measures are regularly reviewed by your company's senior management executive (or board)? How regularly are these reviewed?
5. In your opinion, which of these are considered the most valuable by senior management or the board?
6. Are these measures compared against a) previous year, b) marketing/ business plan c) competitor performance? Are they set against any objectives or targets?
7. Who in the organisation is responsible for the collection of marketing measures e.g. Marketing, Finance, Chief Knowledge Officer?
8. Is this a coordinated process within the organisation (e.g. marketing/finance etc.)? Please elaborate
9. Does the board or senior management receive an overall view of marketing performance (e.g. marketing activities and expenditure)?
10. Is marketing's contribution to the organisation measured using an ROI and does your board or senior management review these numbers?
11. What term does your company use for its main intangible or marketing assets (e.g. brand equity, goodwill, brand health, reputation etc.)?
12. Does your company measure brand equity (using financial valuation) for all its brands or other intangible marketing assets developed by the firm's marketing activities? Can you provide details?
13. Is valuation or growth of other marketing assets reviewed by your board or top executive management?
14. What value does senior management place on marketing metrics in measuring overall business performance? For example, are marketing measures used in an overall business performance measurement system such as a Balanced Scorecard?

15. Are current marketing measures employed synchronised with the firm's overall objectives such as business strategy, corporate objectives and customer feedback. i.e. do measures fit objectives?
16. Are you satisfied with the assessment of marketing performance at senior company levels?
17. What perceptions do you hold of the link between marketing metrics and your company's overall business performance such as profit, sales etc?
18. Generally speaking are you satisfied in the way your company's marketing performance is measured? i.e. are measures used consistent, precise and comprehensive? Are there any areas that require improvement?
19. Do you regard your company as best practice in this area and do you think it could gain a strategic edge over its competitors if it focused more time, efforts and resources on measuring marketing?
20. Are there any other additional comments you would like to make?
21. Do you know any other companies that may be interested in this study?

Interview prompt card

Marketing Metrics Scorecard					
	Collect (Y/N)	Board sees (Y/N)	Highest level seen in the organisation	Frequency Reviewed	Key business objective/KPI
Consumer Intermediate					
Brand Awareness					
Perceived quality					
Consumer satisfaction					
Relevance to consumer					
Perceived differentiation					
Brand/ product knowledge					
Consumer Behaviour					
Number of new consumers					
Customer loyalty/ retention					
Conversions					
Market					
Market share					
Total number of customers					
Relative price					
Trade Customer					
Distribution/Availability					
Customer satisfaction					
Number of complaints					
Relative to competitor					
Relative consumer satisfaction					
Relative perceived quality					
Innovation					
Number of new products					
Revenue of new products					
Margin of new products					
Financial					
Sales					
Gross margins					
Profitability (ROI)					
Other					

REFERENCES

- Aaker, D (1996), *"Building Strong Brands"*, New York Free Press
- Ambler, T (2002), "Market metrics: what should we tell the shareholders?", *Balance Sheet*, 10, 1 pp. 47-50
- Ambler, T (2001), "What does marketing success look like?", *Marketing Management* Spring 2001; Vol. 10, Issue. 1
- Ambler, T (2000), *"Marketing and The Bottom Line"*, Pearson Education, London
- Ambler, T (1999), "Editorial: Where Does the Cash Flow From?", *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15, pp. 705-710
- Ambler, T (1999), "Marketing should be handed to the bean counters", *Marketing*, March 11, p. 7
- Ambler, T (1999), "Why marketing is not measuring up?", *Marketing*, September 24, pp. 24-25
- Ambler, T. Kokkinaki, F. Puntoni, S. Riley, D (2001), *"Assessing Market Performance: The Current State of Metrics"*. Centre for Marketing Working Paper No. 01-903 (September), London Business School
- Ambler, T. Kokkinaki, F (1999). "How does marketing measure up?", *FT Mastering Marketing*, Pearson Education
- Ambler, T. Kokkinaki, F (1997), "Measures of Marketing Success", *Journal of Marketing Management*, 13, pp. 665 – 678
- Ambler, T. Riley, D. (2000) *"Draft Paper, Marketing Metrics: A Review of Performance Measures In Use in The UK and Spain"*, US Marketing Science Institute.
- Appiah-Adu, K. Fyall, A. Singh, S. (2001), "Marketing Effectiveness and Business Performance in the Financial Services Industry", *Journal of Services Marketing*, Vol 15, pp. 18-34
- Bonoma, T. Clark, B (1988), *"Marketing Performance Assessment"*, Harvard Business School Press.
- Brady, J. Davis, (1993), "Marketing's mid-life crisis", *The Mckinsey Quarterly*, (Number 2, pp.17-28)
- Brady, J. Hunter. C, Santiapilla. (2000), "Marketing in the UK", *The Mckinsey Quarterly*, (Number 2, pp.15-17)
- Burbury, R. (2002), "Meet the new marketing manager", *Financial Review Boss* (May), pp. 26-30

- Burns, A and Bush, R (2000), "*Marketing Research*", Prentice Hall International
- The Cap Gemini Ernst & Young Center for Business Innovation (2002), "*The CBI Future Scan*", July, 2002
- The Cap Gemini Ernst & Young Center for Business Innovation (2002), "*Measures that Matter*"
- The Cap Gemini Ernst & Young Center for Business Innovation (2001), "*Perspectives on Business Innovation: Valuing Intangibles*", Issue 7, November, 2001
- Clark, B. (1999) "Marketing Performance Measures: History and Interrelationships", *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15, pp. 711-732
- Court, D. Freeling, A. Leiter, M. Parsons, A (1997), "*If Nike can just do it, why can't we?*", *The McKinsey Quarterly*, (Number 3, pp.24-34)
- Cravens, D (2000), "*Strategic Marketing Management*", McGraw Hill
- Davidson, J (1999), "Transforming The Value of Company Reports Through Marketing Measurement", *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15, pp. 757-777
- Day, G. (1994), "The Capabilities of Market-Driven Organisations", *Journal of Marketing*, Volume 58, issue 4
- Denison, T. McDonald, M (1995), "The role of marketing, past, present and future", *Journal of Marketing Practice: Applied Marketing Science*, Volume 1, Number 1, pp. 54-76
- Denny, N (1999), "Marketing is judged by cash criteria", *Marketing*, May 13, p. 3
- Doyle, P (2001), "Shareholder value based brand strategies", *Brand Management*, Vol 9, No 1, 20-30 September
- Doyle, P. Wong, V (1998), "Marketing and Competitive Performance: an empirical study". *European Journal of Marketing*, Volume 32, Number 5/6 pp. 514-535
- Drucker, P (1995), "The information executives truly need", *Harvard Business Review* (Jan), Volume 73, pp 54-62
- Drucker, P.F. (1973), "*Management*", William Heinemann, London
- Eccles, R (1995), "*The performance measurement manifesto*", The Harvard Business Review, "Measuring Corporate Performance", Harvard Business School Press, 1998.
- Hastings, K. Perry, C. (2000), "Do services exporters build relationships? Some qualitative perspectives", *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, Volume 3, Number 4, pp. 207-214

- Jaworski, B. Kohil, A. (1993), "Marketing Orientation: Antecedents and Consequences", *Journal of Marketing*, 57, pp. 53-70
- Jimenez, C (2002), "Chairman of the Board", *The Weekend Australian, Weekend Money*, October 5-6, 2002, p. 29 and 32
- Kaplan, R. Norton, D (1996), "*Translating strategy into action, The Balanced Scorecard*", Harvard Business School Press
- Kaplan, R. Norton, D (1994), "The Balanced Scorecard – Measures that Drive Performance", *Harvard Business Review* (May-June),
- Kohil, A. Jaworski, J. (1990), "Market Orientation: The construct, research propositions and managerial implications" *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 54 (April), pp. 1-18
- Kokkinaki, F. Ambler, T. (1999), "*Marketing Performance Assessment: An Exploratory Investigation Into Current Practise and The Role of Firm Orientation*", US Marketing Science Institute. Report no. 99-114
- Kotler, P (1999), "Where do we go from here?", *FT Mastering Marketing*, Pearson Education
- Kotler, P, (1984), "*Marketing Management: analysis, planning and control*", Prentice Hall, New Jersey
- KPMG Management Consulting (1999), "*The Role of Marketing*"
- Lafferty, B. Thomas, G. Hult, M. (2001), "*A Synthesis of Contemporary Market Orientation Perspectives*", Vol 35, Issue ½
- Lehmann D, (January 2002), "*MSI Executive Overview: Linking Marketing Decisions to Financial Performance and Firm Value*", US Marketing Science Institute
- Levitt, T (1964), "Marketing Myopia", *Marketing Management and Strategy, A Reader*, Third Edition. Edited: Kotler, Cox K, Prentice Hall 1994
- Lloyd, S (2001), "Brand Power", *Business Review Weekly*, November 29-December 5, 2001, pp. 49-54
- Marketing* (2000), "Marketing still lost in the metrics", August 10, p. 15
- Miles, M. Huberman, M (1994), "*Qualitative Data Analysis*", Sage Publications, London
- Meehan S, Barwise P (1996), "*Do Market-Orientated Businesses Perform Better?*" Centre for Marketing Working Paper, No. 96-103, London Business School
- Moorman, C. Rust, R (1999), "The role of marketing", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol 63, pp. 180-197.

McCullough, R (2000), "Marketing metrics", *Marketing Management*, Volume 9, pp. 64.

Narver, J. Slater, (1990), "The Effect of a Market Orientation on Business Profitability", *Journal of Marketing*, 5 pp. 20-35.

Roberts, J. Styles, C. (2001), Australia's Competitive Advantage: Gaining the Marketing Edge, *Australian Journal of Management*, Volume 26, pp. 105-120

Sekaran, U (2000), "*Business Research Methods*", John Wiley & Sons, New York

Shaw, R. White C, (1999), "Improving Marketing Accountability Through Better Management of the Market Research Process", *Journal of Marketing Management*, 1999. 15, pp. 857-880

Shaw, R and Mazur, L. (1997), "*Marketing Accountability*", FT Books

Simms, J (2001), "Do we need more marketing CEOs?", *Marketing*, April 12, pp. 24-25

Simms, J (2001), "The value of disclosure", *Marketing*, August 2, pp. 26-27

Simms, J (2001), "When marketing and finance meet", *Marketing*, October 11, pp. 20-21

Slater, S. Narver, J (1994), "Does competitive environment moderate the market orientation-performance relationship?", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol 58

Smith, C (2001), "Balance Sheet is not best place to measure brands", *Marketing*, August 2, pp. 21

Srivastava, R. Tasadduq, T, Shervani, A. Fahey, L (1998), "Market Based Assets and Shareholder Value: A Framework for Analysis. *Journal of Marketing*, Vol 62, pp. 2-18.

Styles, C (2000), "*UNSW/AMI Corporate Survey 2000*", University of New South Wales

Superbrands Council (1997), "*Superbrands: an insight into 65 of Australia's superbrands*"

Thakor, M (1996), "Brand origin: conceptualisation and review", *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Volume 13, Issue 3

Trochim, William M (2000). "*The Research Methods Knowledge Base*", 2nd Edition

Wallace, T. (2002), "AFR Boss marketing survey 2002", *Financial Review Boss* (May), pp. 20-25

Zikmund, W (2000), "*Exploring Marketing Research*", Dryden Press, 2000

Hyperlink references

HREF 1: *"Marketers turn to Measure the Impact of Their Initiatives"*

http://knowledge.wharton.upenn.edu.edu/print_version.cfm?articleid=606&catid=4

Accessed 21 August, 2002